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Abstract	This deliverable presents the progress of three key technical components within AD4GD. Section 2 covers
Keywords	Dataspace connectors, Metadata, Data Catalogues, ISO 19115, Data Trustworthiness, Data Quality
Disclaimer	Views and opinions expressed in this deliverable are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union the United Kingdom or Switzerland. Neither the European Union nor United Kingdom nor Switzerland can be held responsible for them

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
HTTP	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
RAM	Reference Architecture Model
REST	Representational State Transfer
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connectors
DCP	Decentralized Claims Protocol
DSP	Dataspace Protocol
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
SPI	Service Provider Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
MVD	Minimum Viable Dataspace
HPC	High Performance Computing
DAT	Dynamic Attribute Token
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
FC	Federated Catalogue
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
FROST	FRaunhofer OpenSource SensorThings-Server
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GeoDCAT	Geospatial Data Catalog Vocabulary
GIS	Geographic Information System
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium

QualityML	Quality Markup Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SOSA	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator
STA	Sensor Things API
STApplus	Sensor Things API plus (extension of STA)
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogues
TAPIS	Tables from OGC APIs for Sensors
UncertML	Uncertainty Markup Language
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
XML	Extensible Markup Language
URL	Universal Resource Locator
URI	Universal Resource Identifier
CRW	Centroid Reflection Wavelength

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document continues the work presented in D4.1, focussing on integration activities. Like D4.1, the text follows the components' architecture defined by D6.1, focussing primarily on three components:

1. Component 2 – Evaluation of Connector Solutions
2. Component 9 – Data catalogue and Metadata
3. Component 11 – Data Trustworthiness Framework

In terms of tasks, this deliverable predominantly discusses work in WP4 “Satellite and Green Deal Data Space Integration”, including tasks 4.2 “Green Deal Data Space Implementation”, 4.3 “Green Data Space integration with third-party services” and 4.4 “Ground truthing and data trustworthiness framework”.

Section 2: Evaluation of Connector Solutions discusses the role of data connectors in creating secure and interoperable dataspace, as highlighted by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA). AD4GD has implemented an IDSA-aligned data connector, integrated with its repository, to facilitate data sharing across different spaces. This connector allows AD4GD to function as both a data provider, exposing pilot datasets, and a data consumer, integrating external data sources. By adopting IDSA standards, AD4GD aligns itself with broader European data initiatives like Gaia-X and FIWARE, aiming to contribute to a unified data ecosystem. The section also describes an initial evaluation of the connector's performance through a test scenario involving data exchange between two IDSA-compliant instances—one within the AD4GD space and an external connector acting as a data consumer. This test demonstrates the potential for seamless data transactions and sets the foundation for further integration in upcoming project deliverables.

Section 3: Data Catalogue and Metadata provides an overview of the AD4GD data and metadata catalogue implemented in GeoNetwork, focusing on its support for ISO 19115-compliant metadata and integration with other dataspace components. GeoNetwork is utilized for organizing geospatial and environmental datasets, providing structured data access through OGC-compliant services like CSW (Catalogue Service for the Web). The section also describes steps for linking metadata with datasets and integrating quality metrics using QualityML.

Having laid the groundwork for data catalogue and metadata representations within the project, Section 4: Data Trustworthiness Framework looks at how these tools can be used to implement a framework for tracking data quality and trustworthiness as it flows through each pilot project. This includes the form and prevalence of uncertainty information attached to external datasets used in the project, methods for estimating uncertainty information when it is missing, uncertainty propagation, ground truthing and standardised representations for this information. We analyse the data flow within each pilot project and discuss approaches to each of these questions.

2 EVALUATION OF CONNECTOR SOLUTIONS

As highlighted by the **International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)** on its first Data Connector Report¹, data connectors are a way to combine many different and heterogeneous data sources in a common place, creating a large pool of available data sets. These data connectors, in turn, create dataspace as protected environments for participants to exchange data according to a fixed set of rules, in the form of data exchange offers and contracts. These are meant to guarantee **data sovereignty, transparency, and fairness**.

Following these principles, AD4GD dataspace instances a data connector, integrated with its data repository. This is intended to assess this component as the common approach to link different dataspace, working both as a data provider by exposing selected pilot datasets, and as a consumer, allowing external sources to be added to pilots.

This section describes the AD4GD connector instance, including the embedded technologies and exposed interfaces, deployed within the AD4GD dataspace. The selected implementation is aligned with the IDSA guidelines in terms of supported functionalities, protocols and integration requirements and reuses existing open-source resources. By adopting the IDSA standard, AD4GD targets to leverage synergies with other pioneering initiatives like Gaia-X, FIWARE or SITRA, and be part of the European repository for all dataspace endeavours.

In the same way, the section also details a first simple test, providing and consuming an HTTP standard dataset to evaluate the integration of the instantiated data connector within the AD4GD dataspace. The evaluation scenario consists of two instances of IDSA compliant data connectors, one directly linked to (and managed by) the AD4GD dataspace which exposes its data catalogue, and an external one, deployed within a different infrastructure, which represents an external dataspace acting as a data consumer. **The primary target is to test a simple data transaction** between these two instances to check components' deployment, protocols' performance and data sharing capabilities. This evaluation test sets up the layout for the actual integration, offering AD4GD datasets and consuming external available offers. This will be detailed in next D4.3.

2.1 DEFINITION OF DATA CONNECTOR

Simplistically, a data connector consists of **software dedicated to integrating different applications, enabling communication between them**. Once configured, the connector establishes a link to extract specific data from a given source (data-source) and write it to a registered software destination (data-sink). In general terms, data connector works through a general API, or a set of specialised ones, which support commands for: i) managing the data connector, and defining data sources (or assets), data offers and contracts for data consuming; ii) data transfers, enabling the data flows between sources and sinks; and iii) negotiation and control of transfers, aimed at authenticating end-users and providers, thus ensuring the transferring process reliability.

The IDSA encourages the use of data connectors for the above purposes, but reinforcing and emphasising data sovereignty. IDSA data connectors are intended for enabling trust and interoperability in data sharing within dataspace and designed to provide data sovereignty. For this purpose, the IDSA provides a global standard and maintains a Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM²) that details the individual components of the International Data Spaces Association (Connector, Metadata Broker, App Store, etc.). This RAM facilitates secure and self-determined data sharing between trusted parties across various ecosystems/dataspace.

¹ IDSA Data Connector Report 2022 https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-Data-Connector-Report-November-2022.pdf

² IDS_RAM <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/ids-ram-4>

Each dataspace instantiates its own data connector, which acts as its corresponding agent to perform data sharing operations. On a simple approach, data exchanges happen between two connectors. Each (IDS) connector (within the IDS standard) enables data exchange services, following the IDS Dataspace Protocol (DSP)³ (Figure 1), which ensures the interoperability among these dataspace. This way, the connector becomes the hub of its dataspace: i) managing the catalogue of its information offers as a registry of its exposed assets (data sources) linked to the specific contracts and policies which give access to them; ii) driving the contracts' negotiation steps to guarantee the identities of the participants (using a common identity provider), the access policies and the data parameters; and finally, iii) supporting the data transfers, acting as a bridge between the original data source and the final data sink.

Figure 1 IDS Dataspace Protocol overview, with dataspace components involved (taken from IDS Dataspace Protocol 2024-1)

2.2 STATE OF THE ART

At the beginning of 2020, the European Commission published⁴ a strategic pathway to leverage data in the best possible way for the sake of the European citizens and the Digital Single Market. This **European Data Strategy** sets out the vision of a **European Data Space**, envisaging a data flow between sectors based on FAIR principles and adhering to standards directly derived from fundamental European values. Along these lines, the International Data Spaces (IDS) initiative aims at cross-sectoral data sovereignty and data interoperability. This is done by specifying an open software architecture (IDS-RAM) and by publishing open source software codes to ensure maximum adoption by the dataspace. This initiative was founded as a non-profit organisation, the **IDS Association (IDSA)**, with currently more than 110 members from more than 20 different countries (Germany, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Spain, etc.). IDSA is also connected to many relevant initiatives across the globe (such as BDVA, FIWARE, the Industrial Internet Consortium, or the Platform Industrie 4.0) and participates in more than 20 European research projects, mainly in the Horizon 2020 program. IDSA is also an integral part of GAIA-X which is aiming at a Federated Data Infrastructure for European ecosystems. All these reasons make the IDSA a truly European initiative, ready to take responsibility for implementing the European Data Strategy and contributing to the creation of the European Data Space.

³ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/dataspace-protocol>

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0066>

In its aim to support the actual needs of the Green Deal Data Space as part of the European Data Strategy, AD4GD aligns its data connector's development with the **IDS-RAM** and the open-source resources it offers.

The concept of **DataSpaces** and the development of **Data connectors** are relatively new, gaining importance with the rise and expansion of the IoT infrastructures over the last decade. Since 2022, the IDSA periodically publishes a **Data Connector Report** which includes an updated and concise State of the Art analysis of its Data Connector model and about all documented interoperable implementations, carried out within different private and public initiatives. This report constitutes a perfect snapshot about all data connectors potentially available in the global market and a vision of the current on-going dataspace in different environments.

At the time of writing this document, the last version of the Data Connector Report⁵ was published in May 2024 and references up to **33 active initiatives** that manage their own Data Connector instance. These instances include both open-source and private connector developments, with different technical readiness levels (TRLs), but all based on the same architecture.

Fostering this data market, the IDSA has built a network of international hubs and competence centres that share knowledge and information about IDS in countries around the world. This is known as the **International Data Spaces network**⁶, which is constituted by the total of its IDS instantiated Data Connectors. Each IDS Connector allows the exchange of data via the exposed Data Endpoints and must be reachable by IDS connectors from other organisations. By deploying its own IDS-compatible data connector, AD4GD aims to contribute to this global network as a data provider and consumer, through the pilots developed within it.

Implementations of data connectors based on the IDS standard can be found as closed source software and as open-source software. To foster the development of new connectors' instances and expand the interoperable European Data Spaces, the IDSA provides several open-source tools, e.g., the **IDS Graduation Scheme**⁷ which provides a set of rules, processes, and criteria to manage these open-source implementations on the IDSA GitHub; the **Data Spaces Radar**⁸ that provides a comprehensive view of various dataspace initiatives worldwide; or the **IDSA GitHub**⁹ itself, includes updated references to the right sources of information, software code, examples, sandbox, etc.

2.2.1 INTERNATIONAL DATA SPACES' (IDS) DATASPACE CONNECTOR

The IDS Dataspace Connector¹⁰ is a common open source project whose development was driven in collaboration with various research institutes and companies. Currently, this project is paused, as its supporters have redirected their efforts to their corresponding connectors' development, till new entities take its control. Nevertheless, it contains an **IDS Connector reference implementation** which follows the specifications of the **IDS Information Model**. This model defines the fundamental concepts for describing actors in a dataspace, their interactions, the resources exchanged by them, and data usage restrictions.¹¹

⁵ https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-Data-Connector-Report-November-2022.pdf

⁶ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/make/network/>

⁷ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/knowledge-base/ids-open-source-strategy/ids-graduation-scheme>

⁸ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/adopt/data-spaces-radar/>

⁹ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/idsa>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/DataspaceConnector>

¹¹ Bader, Sebastian & Pullmann, Jaroslav & Mader, Christian & Tramp, Sebastian & Quix, Christoph & Müller, Andreas & Akyürek, Haydar & Böckmann, Matthias & Imbusch, Benedikt & Theissen-Lipp, Johannes & Geisler, Sandra & Lange, Christoph. (2020). The International Data Spaces Information Model – An Ontology for Sovereign Exchange of Digital Content. 10.1007/978-3-030-62466-8_12.

This baseline deployment integrates the IDS Information Model and uses the **IDS Messaging Services**, that implements the IDS conform messaging handling with other IDS connectors. This supports the usage control for shared assets according to specified policy patterns.

The core component in this repository provides a **REST API** for loading, updating, and deleting resources with local or remote data enriched by its metadata. At the same time, its architecture allows the existing implementation to be adapted as needed for domain-specific requirements.

The **deployment of the Dataspace Connector** (Figure 2) is provided as a **containerized software application**, so it can be easily run in (and ported to) Docker as well as in Kubernetes environments. This is made up of several components:

- The **core dataspace connector** which implements and exposes the REST APIs that give access to the connectors' features: register and manage assets, define exchange contracts, and create offers. It also supports the IDS Messages for catalogues' management (exposing its own catalogue and accessing external ones), driving contracts' negotiations and starting data transfers.
- The **connector data management** container implements the code to support the internal interactions exposed by the connector's APIs: configuration of the whole connector; keeping internal storage of the registered assets, contracts and offers, catalogue's persistence and interactions with the identity provider; a Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS); and original data sources and/or final data sinks connections.
- On top of the data connector container, an optional dataspace connector GUI can make use of the offered APIS to abstract the RESTFUL complexity and offer an user-friendly interface to interact with the data connector, create offers, explore catalogues and program data transfers.
- Other optional components can be added to the basic deployment to help monitoring (e.g. Jaeger¹²), manage the deployment (e.g. Portainer¹³), or specific containers including e.g. connectors for specific repositories (such as min.io).

Figure 2 IDS Connector Components Overview. Taken from IDS Dataspace Connector official github¹⁴

2.2.2 ECLIPSE DATA COMPONENTS' (EDC) CONNECTOR

¹² <https://www.jaegertracing.io/>

¹³ <https://www.portainer.io/>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/DataspaceConnector>

Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC)¹⁵ is a **framework for building dataspace**s, exchanging data securely with ensured data sovereignty. It provides a basic set of features (functional and non-functional) that dataspace implementations can be re-used and customised for dataspace implementations, ensuring interoperability by design. The EDC initiative develops on top of Gaia-X framework and the IDSA Dataspace protocol specifications and involves several active members such as Amadeus, BMW, Fraunhofer, Huawei or Microsoft. In summary, the EDC framework is designed for developers who want to build dataspace implementations on an existing, standards-based framework and adopt and adapt it with their own solutions. For this purpose, and relying on an **open-source Apache License**, the framework updates periodically its outcomes as a set of components and corresponding capabilities required to implement a dataspace. Its main architecture is composed by:

- **EDC Data Connector**, which covers the IDSA *Dataspace connector* and *Data Management* core components (from Figure 2),
- **Identity Hub**, an implementation for the Decentralized Claims Protocol (DCP) specification¹⁶. It contains (and manages) credentials for authorized parties, acting as the identity manager for accessing locally to the dataspace resources and as the identity provider for data transactions.
- **Data Dashboard** (Management UI), as a specific GUI for the EDC Data Connector (*Dataspace Connector GUI* from Figure 2).

From the perspective of AD4GD, the **EDC Data Connector**¹⁷ resource was used for the baseline of our IDSA compliant data connectors' instances. This includes:

- The **Service Provider Interface** (SPI) module contains all necessary interfaces, model classes, enums and programming resources needed to be implemented. These can be modified and customised by the users to extend/adapt the connectors' functionalities.
- The **Core** module contains all the essential implementations that are necessary for the connector to run its basic functionalities: these include the *TransferProcessManager*, the *ProvisionManager* and the *DataFlowManager*, plus the protocol engine and the policy block. A simple description of these functionalities is shown in the Connector's Evaluation section below.
- The **extensions** modules include code that extends the connector's core functionality with additional protocols and/or technologies, needed to link specific data sources, sinks, or extra components, such as MinIO, PostgreSQL, or AWS/Azure-based storage solutions.
- **Data-protocols** add implementations for communication protocols a connector might use, such as the Data Space Protocol (DSP).

2.2.3 SOVITY COMMUNITY EDITION CONNECTOR

Sovity¹⁸ is a Fraunhofer spin-off devoted to the design of dataspace. It supports the activities carried out by the IDSA and contributes to the EDC Connector's functionality with extensions to offer enterprise-ready managed services like "Connector-as-a-Service", out-of-the-box fully configured Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS), and integrations to existing other dataspace technologies.

In general terms, Sovity takes the core and the SPI components from the Eclipse Data Connector and extends their building blocks to create an IDSA compliant baseline deployment that uses PostgreSQL as its persistence layer (that keeps the assets, contracts and offers registries) and provides a custom implementation for the Transfers, Provision and DataFlows managers. In addition, the Sovity connector's functionalities are exposed through several API REST interfaces:

¹⁵ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.edc>

¹⁶ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.dataspace-dcp/governance>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>

¹⁸ <https://sovity.de/en/sovity-en/>

- **Management** API supports the creation of the assets, contracts and offers that compose the dataspace to be managed by the data connector
- **Protocol (DSP)** API drives the data sharing process, implementing the IDSA DataSpace protocol and exposing (and accessing) the dataspace catalogue.
- **Control** and **Public** APIs are intended to ensure the proper execution of the contracts, in terms of identification and authentication of both: providers and consumers agents and perform the data transfers within a secured agent to agent connection.

To enhance the Data Connector features, Sovity develops a set of **extensions** for common dataspace scenarios intended to cover specific properties and functionalities such as policies (“time-intervals”, “always-true”), specific data-base accesses (PostgreSQL), contracts’ templates, deployment tests, etc.

On top of its connector, Sovity also provides a customised **User Interface** (Figure 3), which covers the Eclipse Data Dashboard and relies on the Sovity exposed APIs.

Figure 3 Sovity User Interface example (taken from Sovity EDC UI GitHub¹⁹)

This initiative offers its **Sovity Community Edition**²⁰ an open-source Data Connector’s implementation based on the EDC’s open-source code and combined with Sovity open-source extensions.

2.3 AD4GD EDC INSTANCE (IMPLEMENTATION)

In its aim to achieve the implementation of an AD4GD Green Deal Data Space aligned with the European Green Deal initiative and compliant with the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), a customised deployment of an AD4GD data connector, relying on the IDS Dataspace Protocol, has been evaluated as a solution to integrate our dataspace within the Green Deal Data Spaces ecosystem. The final target of this connector is to expose the AD4GD data catalogue, including the outcomes of its pilots, and serve its datasets according to GDDS standards, as well as being able to incorporate data from other sources from related dataspace.

The development (and deployment) of IDSA compliant dataspace connectors is a work in progress, which is continuously adapted to the specific needs of data exploitation. As mentioned in the State-of-the-Art

¹⁹ <https://github.com/sovity/edc-ui>

²⁰ <https://github.com/sovity/edc-ce#sovity-community-edition-edc-1>

section, this has resulted in a set of proprietary implementations dedicated to cover specific needs, and a set of open solutions, which provide developments with different levels of implementation of the IDS Dataspace protocol. In this sense, and due to the maturity of the provided software, the project selected the EDC connector available components as the baseline to implement its data connector. In addition, and to implement a Minimum Viable Dataspace (MVD) solution, the DAPS service provided by Sovity is also considered and, potentially, some other Sovity extensions are to be explored for future deployments.

Figure 4 presents a functional view of the AD4GD data connector instance (running in ATOS premises/tenant), including the data sources mentioned in D5.1 and D6.1 and the connection with an external data connector instance (running in PSNC premises/tenant), to perform a data transaction. The interfaces and building blocks are described in next subsection.

Figure 4 AD4GD Data Connector instance (ATOS tenant). Functional view

For this first approach, the target is to evaluate the deployed architecture for the AD4GD Dataspace connector, performing a simple provider-consumer trial and using a generic data source. This validates the implementation for further tests, creating and using the AD4GD catalogue.

2.3.1 CONNECTORS' DEPLOYMENT (ARCHITECTURE)

The deployment aimed to test connectivity between different tenants (provider and consumer agents), requiring the implementation of critical components of a **Minimum Viable Dataspace (MVD)**. The architecture follows a provider-consumer model, with the necessary infrastructure deployed as shown in (Figure 5). In this setup, the **ATOS tenant** (provider) includes services responsible for providing data, while the **PSNC tenant** (consumer) includes services for retrieving and storing the provided data. In the absence of a federated catalogue (FC), the **Provider Connector** (ATOS) temporarily fulfils this role. Each service serves a crucial role within the dataspace ecosystem. The key components are described below:

- **Data Dashboards** offer a user-friendly interface (UI), enabling users to manage connectors without the complexity of using the connector's API directly. The current dashboards are modified versions of the open-source *EDC Data Dashboard project*²¹ adapted for the project's specific needs. This dashboard is used to illustrate the connector's evaluation sub-section.
- **AD4GD Connectors** are central elements of the dataspace, providing secure, reliable, and structured data exchange between participants. Each connector relies on persistent storage to maintain information generated by the control plane (e.g., assets, contract definitions, policies, and transfer history). These are the core blocks for both connectors supporting the IDS protocol (control plane), and the management plane (transfers, provision and dataflows managers). The connectors expose APIs that allow for fine-grained control and management of their operations. These take the EDC connector for the implementation and some Sovity approaches for the exposed APIs.

²¹ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/DataDashboard>

- **Identity Provider (DAPS)** functions as an Identity Access Management (IAM) layer, issuing Dynamic Attribute Tokens (DAT) to authenticated and verified participants, ensuring secure and authenticated connections. The authorization process is based on a centralized OAuth 2.0²² authorization framework, with the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) acting as the identity provider. The implementation of the identity provider is based on the Sovity DAPS, which is built on Keycloak²³.
- **Backend (consumer)** extends the connector's data plane by providing functionality to persist transferred assets into a custom storage solution, such as MinIO. This service is invoked as a callback once the data transfer process reaches the 'Started' state.

The connector architecture includes several APIs, each serving a specific role in enabling, managing, and facilitating data exchanges within the dataspace. Below is an outline of each API and its purpose:

- **Core API** (/api) provides utility endpoints such as health checks and status monitoring.
- **Control API** (/control) responsible for low-level interactions with the control plane. Used by the data plane to notify the control plane when data transfer completes or fails. It also coordinates the communication between control and data planes during data exchanges.
- **Management API** (/management) manages high-level interactions with the entities in the control plane, such as assets, policies, and contracts. Exposes access to the dataset catalogue.
- **Protocol API** (/protocol) facilitates contract negotiations and interactions through standardized data exchange protocols. While multiple protocols can potentially be supported, the current out-of-the-box implementation uses the Dataspace Protocol (DSP).
- **Public API** (/public) grants access to assets during the data transfer process. Access is secured through an authorization mechanism that requires an authorization code, issued as part of the transfer procedure.

²² <https://oauth.net/2/>

²³ <https://github.com/sovity/sovity-daps>

Figure 5 Deployment architecture UML diagram

2.3.2 AD4GD SIMPLE TEST SCENARIO

The target of this first evaluation test is to validate the selected connector’s design and software pieces, and its deployment within the AD4GD dataspace, as a suitable tool (component) to create, manage and expose the data catalogue of AD4GD project, according to IDS standards and communication protocols. The simple test scenario uses two instances of the data connector with the same architecture as shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5. These instances correspond to the first version of the AD4GD data connector developed by PSCN, which a simple Web User Interface design and implementations for the Management, Control, Protocol and Public APIs, based on EDC Data connector version 0.7.0. This first version focuses on the creation of the data catalogue and the execution of data transfers and does not implement the integration with the DAPS module. This will be validated in further testing for the final version of the AD4GD connector and reported in D4.3. With this in mind, the simple test scenario (Figure 6) consists of:

- **HTTP Data source:** the first version of the AD4GD data connector (like its baseline, the EDC connector) natively supports HTTP data feeds. To create a first asset, an open FIWARE Context Broker instance has been selected. This Context Broker provides a HTTP NGSI API Rest²⁴ to create

²⁴ https://wirecloud.readthedocs.io/en/stable/development/ngsi_api/

and retrieve NGSI entities, in the form of JSON files. For this purpose, the open SmartDataModels' testbed, provided by the FIWARE Foundation²⁵, is used. This Context Broker already contains a set of testing IoT context entities that will be used as data to be shared through the AD4GD provider's data connector instance. At the time of these tests, AD4GD data sources were not yet available. These will be used for final evaluation tests.

- **Provider's Data Connector Instance**, deployed in the AD4GD HPC Cluster (D5.1) (ATOS tenant) as part of the AD4GD dataspace. It will act as the data provider, by defining the asset for the Context Broker data source and the policies and contracts necessary to expose this asset within the AD4GD catalogue. This also supports the AD4GD Data Catalogue.
- **Consumer Data Connector Instance**, running in PSNC tenant, will act as the data consumer, connecting to the AD4GD instance, accessing its data catalogue, selecting the offer that includes the Context Broker data source and signing the corresponding contract.
- **Consumer Data Sink**, managed by the consumer connector instance, defines the final repository to store the required data from the producer connector. The current version of the connector supports local storage (download the requested file locally in the server running the consumer connector) or using a MinIO repository instance through its S3 interface to capture and store the acquired file.

Figure 6 Simple test scenario, including the components to validate a data transfer (JSON file) between connectors.

The diagram (Figure 7) represents the complete process of establishing a connection and transferring data between the consumer and provider connectors. The process is divided into four main steps:

1. **Catalogue Request:** The consumer's control plane requests a dataset catalogue from the provider, containing available data offers. These offers are used by the consumer to initiate contract negotiations.
2. **Contract Negotiation:** The consumer sends a contract offer, which the provider validates. Upon successful negotiation, both the provider and consumer store the contract agreement in their respective databases.
3. **Transfer Process Control:** After the contract negotiation is finalized, the consumer can initiate a data transfer process for the agreed asset. This is the first phase of the data transfer, where the consumer receives an authorization code upon reaching the "Started" state, allowing for the data transfer to begin.

²⁵ <https://smartdatamodels.org/>

4. **Data Transfer:** Triggered as a callback once the transfer reaches the "Started" state, the consumer's data plane uses the authorization code obtained in the previous step to request and retrieve the data from the provider's data plane.

During each interaction between the connectors, the attached Dynamic Attribute Token (DAT) is verified to ensure the validity of the connection. Current tests (first version of the Connectors' deployment) use a mocked DAPS service to support this verification. The final version of D4.3 will integrate with the real DAPS module. If the provider encounters an unknown signature, it requests the Identity Provider (DAPS) to retrieve updated keys and ensure continued secure communication.

Figure 7 Data transfer process UML diagram

2.4 CONNECTOR'S EVALUATION

The following sequence diagrams represent the detailed steps involved in a complete data transfer scenario between consumer and provider connectors. Each diagram focuses on a specific phase of the process, illustrating interactions between key components in the dataspace ecosystem.

The **Web User Interface** deployed in both connectors' instances rely on the **Management; Control; Protocol;** and **Public APIs** mentioned in previous section, so, internally implement the calls pointed in the diagrams. Screen captures from these Web UI are used to better illustrate the evaluation tests.

2.4.1 ENTITIES CREATION

The first sequence diagram (Figure 8) demonstrates the entity creation process. This process is fundamental to initializing the data-sharing scenario, as each entity must be registered in the system before data can be exchanged. The key components involved are the **Management API** and the control plane, which manage the creation and persistence of these entities.

Figure 8 Entity creation process UML diagram

In the diagram (Figure 8), the API path “/management/v3/{entityType}” is used, where the value of **entityType** determines the type of entity being created. Depending on the provided **entityType**, the system will create an asset, policy, contract definition (a.k.k offer), or another required entity.

For the dataset asset, the FIWARE Context Broker is used. Request in Figure 9 retrieves all IoT entities stored representing “vehicles” according to the NGSI Vehicles Smart Data Model within a JSON file. Figure 10 uses the provider’s Web UI to create the asset **EVAL01-NGSICB-Test01** that accesses this data source.

```
https://smartdatamodels.org:1026/v2/entities?type=Vehicle
```

Figure 9 NGSI Context Entity query.

Figure 10 Provider’s WEB User Interface: creation of a new Asset screen.

EDC Demo Policies

Getting Started

Catalog

Contracts

Transfers

Contract Definitions

Policies

Assets

ID*

EVAL01-Policy-ALL-Test01

Assignee

Eval01-Test-NGSI

Assigner

AD4GD

Permissions (JSON)

all

Prohibitions (JSON)

none

Obligations (JSON)

none

Save Cancel

Figure 11 Provider's WEB User Interface: creation of a new Policy screen.

The EDC **Policy** engine allows for specifying requirements to access data. **Policies** may include various optional conditions such as time-based access windows, IP restrictions, data usage limitations, or even specific compliance conditions (e.g., GDPR). The **Assignee** field is the individual granted data access under conditions defined in the policy. The **Assigner** field specifies the entity responsible for defining and enforcing the policy, this field can enforce restrictions based on organizational policies, contractual obligations, or legal requirements, thereby ensuring that access aligns with internal and external compliance requirements. Policies are loaded into EDC connector via the **Management API** using a policy definition. For the simple transaction test carried out here, no specific policies have been defined, allowing for an open access transaction of the datasets. For the final tests to be carried out within the AD4GD Dataspace final deployment, several policies will be included.

EDC Demo Contract Definitions

Getting Started

Catalog Browser

Contracts

Transfers

Contract Definitions

Policies

Assets

Search definitions

1 - 3 of 3

Create contract definition

Id*

EVAL01-Offer-NGSI-Test01

Access policy*

EVAL01-Policy-ALL-Test01

Contract policy*

EVAL01-Policy-ALL-Test01

Assets

EVAL01-NGSICB-Test01

Create Cancel

1

Figure 12 Provider's WEB User Interface: creation of a new Contract Definition/Offer screen.

The **combination** of an **asset** (or several ones) with a set of **policies** (access and contract policies) creates a **Contract Definition**, also known as an **Offer** which automatically is added to the **connector's catalogue**. The **Access Policy** manages how data is accessed and transferred, ensuring that the process is secure and compliant. On the other hand, the **Contract Policy** handles the negotiation process, setting the terms and responsibilities for the Contract Definition.

2.4.2 CATALOGUE PUBLICATION (PROVIDER)

The second diagram (Figure 13) outlines the access catalogue process, where the **consumer dashboard** requests and receives the dataset catalogue from the consumer's control plane (steps 1-4).

Figure 13 Provider's catalogue access UML diagram

Periodically the consumer checks and fetches the latest dataset catalogue from the provider which in our case fulfils the role of the **federated catalogue (FC)**. This catalogue contains available data offers that the consumer can evaluate before proceeding with contract negotiations. This phase ensures the consumer has visibility into the provider's data offerings through secure API interactions. Figure 14 shows the provider's connector instance catalogue, showing the offer created by combining the defined asset with its assigned policies.

Figure 14 Consumer’s WEB User Interface: Catalogue screen.

2.4.3 CONTRACT NEGOTIATION

The third diagram (Figure 15) details the **Contract Negotiation**. After fetching the catalogue, the consumer initiates contract negotiations by sending a contract offer to the provider. The provider validates the offer (in-between steps 7-8), and upon successful negotiation, both the consumer and provider store the contract agreement (steps 8-12). This process is essential for establishing the terms under which the data will be shared, ensuring compliance with policies and requirements defined during entity creation. Through the Web User Interface, this negotiation process is triggered by clicking on the “Negotiate” button in Figure 14 from the consumer’s connector instance (PSNC tenant).

Figure 15 Contract negotiation UML diagram.

In step 3 of the contract negotiation process, when the consumer sends a request to the provider, it attaches a **Dynamic Attribute Token (DAT)**, which must be validated to authorize the consumer. Within

this simple evaluation test, this is implemented using default DAT Service/DAPS. Normally, the provider stores the public key either in memory (cache) or the filesystem, reducing the need for continuous interaction with the DAPS service. However, in this specific scenario, it is assumed that the public key has changed. As a result, the provider must contact the DAPS service to retrieve the updated public key, which is then used to validate the DAT token and ensure the legitimacy of the consumer's request (steps 4-5).

2.4.4 DATA TRANSFER MANAGEMENT

This sequence diagram (Figure 16) combines both the **Transfer Process Control (steps 1–10)** and **Data Transfer (steps 11–20)** into a single cohesive process. It illustrates the full flow of how the consumer requests and retrieves data from the provider after a successful contract negotiation.

Figure 16 Transfer Process Control and Data Transfer UML diagram.

Transfer Process Control (steps 1–10): After the contract negotiation is finalized, the **consumer initiates a transfer process** for the selected asset. The consumer's control plane sends a transfer request to the provider, which triggers the provider to validate the contract and prepare the requested data. Upon successful validation, the transfer process reaches the "Started" state, and the consumer is issued an authorization code. This code is crucial for authorizing the subsequent data transfer. From the Consumer's connector Web UI, this process is triggered by clicking on "Transfer" button (Figure 17).

Figure 17 Consumer's WEB User Interface: Available (signed) contracts/offers screen.

Data Transfer (steps 11–20): Once the transfer process reaches the "Started" state, the consumer's data plane can proceed with requesting the actual data from the provider's data plane. Using the authorization code obtained earlier, the consumer securely retrieves the data from the provider. Throughout the process, both control and data planes interact to ensure that the transfer is completed according to the agreed-upon terms and policies.

Figure 18 shows the Start transfer screen on Consumer's side. In this test, the transfer will store the requested dataset in a local file (*EVAL01-NGSICB-Test01.json*). Figure 19 shows the list of executed transfers on both sides, provider and consumer connectors. These registries show a successful transaction process and therefore, a successful evaluation test: **the AD4GD connector reference deployment covers the IDS connection compliance function for the AD4GD dataspace.**

Figure 18 Consumer's WEB User Interface: Start Transfer screen.

Transfer History				Transfer History			
b8b8107f-0ab5-496a-9894-eb56c34d3c5a	TERMINATED	23/10/2024	Test-NGSI-Asset-01	e72e06a5-fba6-4bd4-8c3a-2db128ad94b	STARTED	16/10/2024	Test-asset-ada9d
277b0cd5-ce6d-4866-88c7-e9d5a0070407	STARTED	24/10/2024	EVALD1-NGSICB-Test01	b1afbb9c-12c6-41c7-a363-f3a6fced7c8	STARTED	16/10/2024	dw-asset1
498c57c5-9f08-406f-b745-a6er04d6554e	STARTED	23/10/2024	Test-NGSI-Asset-01	02470d72-b6df-46fc-a665-83391fdd594	STARTED	8/10/2024	dw-asset1
397/c9ec-42a8-4ac6-b867-91065fb635c0	STARTED	23/10/2024	Test-NGSI-Asset-01	02470d72-b6df-46fc-a665-83391fdd594	STARTED	17/10/2024	Test-asset-ada9d
721ec626-e73e-418f-aeaf	STARTED	24/10/2024	EVALD1-NGSICB-Test01	b1afbb9c-12c6-41c7-a363-f3a6fced7c8	STARTED	16/10/2024	Test-asset-ada9d
5b41007b48c3-a5f6ba72-4ea8-4797-b34c-b626e134e661	STARTED	25/10/2024	EVALD1-NGSICB-Test01	f3a6fced7c8-30ec-21a0-afdd-4fe7-bdb1-2d7ae11b36d	STARTED	25/10/2024	EVAL-01-NGSICB-Test01
				ae9ad7a58-2887-4cad-8a9d-eeec2e27f1abf	STARTED	16/10/2024	Test-asset-ada9d
				90/abf2e-b111-4379-bdb7-83d6a471c6dc	STARTED	16/10/2024	dw-asset1
				bae0dd7f-7de4-4be9-9ab7-0b43e719919d	STARTED	8/10/2024	dw-asset1
				6f08346c-c130-4d81-b264-f681980c0b24	STARTED	17/10/2024	Test-asset-ada9d
				290444ba-020e-4194-a377-df18d0684e9d	STARTED	16/10/2024	Test-asset-ada9d
				37c22240-85a7-4a80-8110-c0020d109f86	STARTED	25/10/2024	EVAL-01-NGSICB-Test01
							6327c36b-6532-477c-9a27-597b7e3322d8
							4a31b26-0dda-4b40-ae5-285e37c0a75c
							b2706152-7a71-4a85-9f6c-9a4a8151151
							6327c36b-6532-477c-9a27-597b7e3322d8
							6327c36b-6532-477c-9a27-597b7e3322d8
							30ae21a0-a00d-4fe7-bdb1-2b7ae11b36d1

Figure 19 Provider's and Consumer's WEB User Interfaces: Transfers' list (history) screen seen at both sides of the transaction process.

3 DATA CATALOGUE AND METADATA

This section describes the AD4GD data and metadata catalogue implementation within GeoNetwork, including practices for documenting ISO 19115-compliant metadata, and the methods used to connect the catalogue with other technical components in the dataspace, such as accessing it via OGC CSW (Catalog Service for the Web) and connecting it with other services like OGC Sensor Things API (STA), STApplus (extension of STA), TAPIS (Tables from OGC APIs for Sensors), and the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) catalogue.

3.1 DATA CATALOGUES

Data catalogues play a crucial role in organizing and managing datasets, providing users with a structured approach to discover, access, and utilize data effectively. In the context of open data and geospatial information, several standards and platforms have emerged to facilitate this process.

A catalogue system typically includes some or all of the following components: support for one or more metadata standards, enabling the structured description and discoverability of datasets across platforms; a user-facing interface, often a web portal, that allows users to search, browse, and access the data; APIs for accessing data or metadata, which provide programmatic access for automated workflows and integrations with external systems; and administrative tools for managing the system, including features for updating metadata, monitoring usage, and ensuring data integrity and compliance.

3.1.1 METADATA STANDARDS

Of the metadata standards that exist, those most applicable to the needs of a data catalogue are:

1. **ISO 19115²⁶**: A comprehensive metadata standard specifically designed for the description of geographic information and services. It is widely used in geospatial systems to ensure that geographic datasets, such as maps, satellite imagery, and environmental monitoring data, are described in a standardized way. ISO 19115 provides detailed metadata about spatial and temporal extent, data quality, coordinate systems, and geographic coverage. It is typically serialized in XML (ISO 19139) and is tailored for detailed, high-precision descriptions necessary for geospatial applications. ISO 19115 focuses heavily on geospatial and environmental datasets, making it more difficult to apply to non-geographic data. Many domains now use “application profiles” as the bases of their metadata models, **which** are recommended subsets of ISO 19115, occasionally with additional terms included as formal extensions to the standard.
2. **DCAT (Data Catalogue Vocabulary)²⁷**: An RDF-based metadata standard designed specifically to support interoperability between data catalogues on the web. Unlike ISO 19115, DCAT is not geospatially focused and is more versatile, being applicable to a wide variety of datasets.
3. **GeoDCAT-AP²⁸**: An extension of the DCAT application profile for data portals in Europe that included terms from both ISO 19115:2003 and those defined in the framework of the INSPIRE Directive of the European Union.
4. **Dublin Core²⁹**: A general-purpose metadata standard used across various disciplines, particularly for library, archive, and information science. It defines a simple set of metadata elements to describe digital resources such as documents, images, and websites.

²⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/26020.html>

²⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

²⁸ <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/releases/>

²⁹ https://www.dublincore.org/resources/glossary/dublin_core/

5. **Schema.org**³⁰: This standard includes metadata for various data types, including datasets. It is typically used, serialised as JSON-LD, to embed structured metadata into HTML pages that can be parsed by search engines crawlers, allowing them to better understand and display datasets and other types of content.

While these standards are relevant to creating metadata at a dataset level, it should be noted that there are complementary metadata standards that describe data at the observation level. An example of this would be the **Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA)**³¹ model, which will be discussed later.

3.1.2 SERIALIZATIONS

Each of the above metadata standards may be serialised to different formats. Most metadata standards are defined in Resource Description Framework (RDF)³². **RDF** is a widely used standard for representing information that is based on subject, predicate, object triples. The RDF standard describes multiple serialisation formats for storing and transforming it, examples of which include Extensible Markup Language (**XML**) and **Turtle**³³. However, with the increasing popularity of JSON, an encoding from RDF to JSON called **JSON-LD** (JSON for Linking Data) is a popular alternative. As mentioned above, Schema.org metadata is typically embedded into HTML pages as JSON-LD (Figure 20). JSON-LD is a serialisation of RDF that targets JSON, it is a format defined 'on top' of JSON that represents RDF.

```
<script type="application/ld+json">
{
  "@context": "https://schema.org/",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "name": "NCDC Storm Events Database",
  "description": "Storm Data is provided by the National Weather Service (NWS) and contain statistics on...",
  "url": "https://catalog.data.gov/dataset/ncdc-storm-events-database",
  "sameAs": "https://gis.ncdc.noaa.gov/geoportal/catalog/search/resource/details.page?id=gov.noaa.ncdc:C00510",
  "identifier": [ "https://doi.org/10.1000/182",
                 "https://identifiers.org/ark:/12345/fk1234" ],
  "keywords": [
    "ATMOSPHERE > ATMOSPHERIC PHENOMENA > CYCLONES",
  ]
}
```

Figure 20 Provider's This abridged JSON-LD snippet was embedded in the HTML of a website documenting the NCDC Storm Events Database. It is valid JSON that conforms, in this case, to a Dataset record from the Schema.org vocabulary.

Many catalogue implementations that serve human readable HTML sites embed JSON-LD descriptions of the objects they describe using Schema.org models. The **Radiant Earth STAC Browser**³⁴ does this, as does **GeoNetwork**³⁵ and the US Government **Open Data Portal Data.Gov**³⁶ and many more³⁷.

3.1.3 CATALOGUE SYSTEMS

Multiple catalogue systems build upon these metadata standards to provide a full data catalogue.

GeoNetwork is an open-source catalogue application specifically tailored to managing spatially referenced resources. It supports the ISO 19115 metadata standard, making it highly suited for geospatial data

³⁰ <https://schema.org/>

³¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>

³² <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts>

³³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

³⁴ <http://schema.org/>

³⁵ <https://github.com/geonetwork/core-geonetwork/pull/3714>

³⁶ <http://data.gov/>

³⁷ <https://github.com/json-ld/json-ld.org/wiki/Users-of-JSON-LD>

management and sharing. It provides a user-friendly interface for discovering and publishing descriptions of datasets. One of its strengths is its ability to efficiently handle geographic metadata, allowing organizations to centralize spatial data description from different sources and make it accessible through standardized web services such as OGC-compliant interfaces (e.g., CSW, WMS, WFS). It also offers robust administrative tools for managing metadata quality, access controls, and user roles.

Similarly, **Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN)**³⁸ is a widely adopted open-source data management platform designed to facilitate the discovery, sharing, and publication of open data. It supports a wide range of metadata standards, though mainly DCAT, and is versatile enough to handle diverse types of datasets, not just geospatial data. CKAN is well known for its user-friendly web interface, allowing users to easily search and access datasets. Additionally, it provides a powerful API, making it possible for developers to build custom applications that integrate with CKAN-based catalogues.

In the geospatial domain, specialized catalog standards such as SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) and **OGC API Records** further enhance data accessibility.

STAC³⁹ is the combination of a minimal metadata standard and an API specification. It focuses on providing a simple way to describe geospatial data in time and space, making it highly suitable for satellite imagery and Earth observation data but it is not immediately useful for other datasets. It does however support community extensions⁴⁰ that allow its metadata schema to be extended. There are also web based browsers build to view STAC API endpoints such a STAC Brower. While STAC itself is not currently compatible with JSON-LD⁴¹, the STAC Browser automatically exposes JSON-LD metadata conforming to Schema.org.

3.2 THE GEONETWORK DATA CATALOGUE AND ISO 19115

In AD4GD, we have chosen GeoNetwork (version 4.0.6.0) as the system to catalogue the data consumed and produced within the project, following the ISO 19115 standard. A general view of the public catalogue is offered in Figure 21. The catalogue is accessible at: <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd>

Figure 21 General view of AD4GD GeoNetwork public data catalogue.

³⁸ <https://ckan.org/>

³⁹ <https://stacspec.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/radianteearth/stac-browser>

⁴¹ <https://github.com/radianteearth/stac-spec/blob/master/best-practices.md>

In the next subsections the different ISO 19115 versions are revised, a list of specific aspects that have been considered to document ISO compliant metadata within GeoNetwork are exposed, and the ADG4D solutions for connecting the catalogue with other technical components in the dataspace are proposed.

3.2.1 VERSIONS OF ISO 19115

ISO19115 has undergone several revisions since its creation in 2003. The initial version, **ISO 19115:2003**, established the foundation for geospatial metadata, defining a comprehensive set of elements to describe the content, quality, spatial and temporal extent, and distribution of geographic datasets. This version primarily focuses on dataset descriptions, making it well-suited for describing geospatial data such as maps, satellite imagery, and environmental monitoring information.

The most significant update came with **ISO 19115-1:2014**, which introduced several improvements over the original standard. This revision included enhanced support for metadata about services, such as web mapping services and geospatial data services, reflecting the growing importance of service-based architectures in geospatial systems. It also expanded the metadata model to better support the description of complex datasets and provided better alignment with related standards like ISO 19119 for services. In parallel, **ISO 19115-2:2009** was developed to extend the standard to cover imagery, gridded data, and other remote sensing datasets, providing specialized metadata elements to describe sensor characteristics and observation processes. It also includes an extension of the lineage model useful beyond imagery.

As of **ISO 19115-1:2018**, the latest version continues to refine the standard by addressing user feedback and improving interoperability with other international metadata standards. This ensures that ISO 19115 remains a critical tool for managing geographic metadata, helping organizations improve data discoverability and interoperability in an increasingly connected and data-driven world.

3.2.2 SPECIFIC ASPECTS TO DOCUMENT ISO 19115 COMPLIANT METADATA IN GEONETWORK

We opted to use **ISO 19115:2003** as it remains the most widely implemented version of the standard, such as in the Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe (INSPIRE) implementing rules⁴². While ISO 19115-1 has been available for several years, its adoption is still limited, with relatively few implementations currently in use.

GeoNetwork offers **native support for ISO 19115 and its XML schema ISO 19139** and an online metadata editor with a customizable template system. In essence, the GeoNetwork interface is structured in sections according to the ISO 19115 metadata classes (Figure 22) which include: Identification, Distribution, Quality, Spatial rep. Ref. System, Content, Metadata, Portrayal, Constrains, Maintenance, Schema info.

⁴² https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/publications/inspire-metadata-implementing-rules-technical-guidelines-based-en-iso-19115-and-en-iso-19119_en

Figure 22 Mapping between ISO 19115:2003 Core Metadata Elements (top, red square) and GeoNetwork editor tabs (bottom, blue square) numbered from 1 to 11, showing how GeoNetwork organizes these elements for easier metadata editing.

GeoNetwork allows for different user roles (e.g., reviewer, editor, administrator). CREAM is responsible for the administration of the AD4GD catalogue. All partners have credentials to access as editors and as reviewers to create and maintain records in the catalogue. Once records are mature enough, they are declared public and made visible to everyone.

The creation of a metadata record in GeoNetwork can be performed according to the different options available:

- Creation of a new record based on an empty template (Figure 23)
- Creation of a new record based on an existing record already in the catalogue
- Importing external XML or other metadata files.

Figure 23 List of AD4GD tailored ISO19139 templates available in GeoNetwork.

3.2.2.1 HOW TO CONNECT METADATA TO DATA

After providing discovery of the relevant resources (datasets), the most important purpose of the catalogue is to provide metadata by which one can access the resources described. In ISO 19115:2003 the MD_Distribution class (Figure 24) contains this information and provides the possibility to describe online access methods for the digital distribution of a dataset (MD_DigitalTransferOptions), identification of the distributor (MD_Distributor) and the format of the distribution (MD_Format).

Figure 24 Detailed view of ISO 19115 MD_Distribution.

One relevant feature of GeoNetwork in contrast with other catalogues revised is the possibility to store data as attachments to the metadata records that then can be linked and accessed from external services and referenced from the distribution metadata. This can be performed from the Associated resources GeoNetwork editor panel (Figure 25), which allows for any type of online resources (GIS vector and raster files, CSV, graphics, documents, pdf files and any other content) to be associated to a metadata record. A document (dataset) can be attached by drag&dropping the corresponding file store area or selecting it from the local disc. When uploaded, by clicking on the new document, a link to the document is automatically created (the endpoint of which can be manually customized). The action on clicking over the new file is necessary, otherwise the link to the resource will not be automatically populated in the metadata distribution info. The same mechanism can be used to upload a thumbnail (browse image); that makes the presentation of each record more visual.

Figure 25 Associated resources GeoNetwork panel.

Finally, the ISO 19115 entity MD_Format can be used to provide a description of the format of the data to be distributed. This process creates a Distribution information that can be seen in GeoNetwork Distribution tab as exemplified in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Example of Distribution information in AD4GD GeoNetwork.

The same information can be seen in the MD_Distribution section of the related XML metadata file, as exemplified in Figure 27.

```

<gmd:distributionInfo>
  <gmd:MD_Distribution>
    <gmd:distributionFormat>
      <gmd:MD_Format>
        <gmd:name>
          <gco:CharacterString>CSV</gco:CharacterString>
        </gmd:name>
        <gmd:version gco:nilReason="unknown">
          <gco:CharacterString/>
        </gmd:version>
      </gmd:MD_Format>
    </gmd:distributionFormat>
    <gmd:transferOptions>
      <gmd:MD_DigitalTransferOptions>
        <gmd:onLine>
          <gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
            <gmd:linkage>
              <gmd:URL>https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/srv/api/records/63ae32b2-2f5c-418a-bd72-439d17b3131c/attachments/Hundekehlesee.csv</gmd:URL>
            </gmd:linkage>
            <gmd:protocol>
              <gco:CharacterString>WWW.LINK-1.0-http-link</gco:CharacterString>
            </gmd:protocol>
            <gmd:name>
              <gco:CharacterString>Hundekehlesee.csv</gco:CharacterString>
            </gmd:name>
          </gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
        </gmd:onLine>
      </gmd:MD_DigitalTransferOptions>
    </gmd:transferOptions>
  </gmd:MD_Distribution>
</gmd:distributionInfo>

```

Figure 27 Example of Distribution information in XML.

This process has been documented step-by-step in AD4GD GitHub, at: <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-GeoNetwork?tab=readme-ov-file#linking-to-documents-stored-in-the-geonetwork-as-attachments>

3.2.2.2 HOW TO EXPRESS THE SEMANTICS OF THE DATA (VARIABLE + UNITS OF MEASURE) AND KEYWORDS

One challenge in AD4GD is to find semantic interoperability solutions for integration of heterogenous data in the GDDS. One manner is starting by encoding and linking data concepts to ISO 19115 MD_Keywords (Figure 28).

Figure 28 Detailed view ISO 19115 MD_Keywords.

The ISO19139 XML schema implementation adds the possibility to transform any string into a link. This is done by replacing <gco:CharacterString> by a <gmx:anchor>. Via this mechanism, it is possible to link individual keywords for variables to their definitions in the context of a related thesaurus or vocabulary. In the same way, in CI_Citation class (Figure 29) it is also possible to associate a URL to a Citation of a thesaurus as a "collection of concepts" using a link in the title (the revised ISO 19115-1 already have a URI in Citation but not the original ISO19115:2003).

<<DataType>> CI_Citation	
+	title : CharacterString
+	alternateTitle [0..*] : CharacterString
+	date [1..*] : CI_Date
+	edition [0..1] : CharacterString
+	editionDate [0..1] : Date
+	identifier [0..*] : MD_Identifier
+	citedResponsibleParty [0..*] : CI_ResponsibleParty
+	presentationForm [0..*] : CI_PresentationFormCode
+	series [0..1] : CI_Series
+	otherCitationDetails [0..1] : CharacterString
+	collectiveTitle [0..1] : CharacterString
+	ISBN [0..1] : CharacterString
+	ISSN [0..1] : CharacterString

Figure 29 Detailed view of CI_Citation.

This solution can be seen in the fragment of XML presented Figure 30.

```

<gmd:descriptiveKeywords>
  <gmd:MD_Keywords>
    <gmd:keyword>
      <gmx:Anchor xlink:href="https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabularyconcept/air/pollutant/6002"
        xlink:type="simple">PM1</gmx:Anchor>
    </gmd:keyword>
    <gmd:keyword>
      <gmx:Anchor xlink:href="http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/current/YUDG9DXK/"
        xlink:type="simple">PM2.5</gmx:Anchor>
    </gmd:keyword>
    <gmd:thesaurusName>
      <gmd:CI_Citation>
        <gmd:title>
          <gmx:Anchor xlink:href="http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/current/"
            xlink:type="simple">Climate and Forecast Standard Names</gmx:Anchor>
        </gmd:title>
        <gmd:date>
          <gmd:CI_Date>
            <gmd:date>
              <gco:Date>2024-09-04</gco:Date>
            </gmd:date>
            <gmd:dateType>
              <gmd:CI_DateTypeCode codeList="http://standards.iso.org/iso/19139/resources/gmxCodeLists.xml#CI_DateTypeCode"
                codeListValue="creation"/>
            </gmd:dateType>
          </gmd:CI_Date>
        </gmd:date>
      </gmd:CI_Citation>
    </gmd:thesaurusName>
  </gmd:MD_Keywords>
</gmd:descriptiveKeywords>
  
```

Figure 30 XML fragment showing keywords and links to individual definitions in the context of a related thesaurus.

The result in GeoNetwork is presented in Figure 31. Each Keyword text become a hyperlink that can be clicked and redirects to the individual definition.

Figure 31 GeoNetwork Visual result of encoded link data concepts to ISO 19115 keywords.

This process has been documented step-by-step in AD4GD GitHub, at:

<https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-GeoNetwork?tab=readme-ov-file#how-to-encode-link-data-concepts-to-iso-19115-keyworks>.

3.2.2.3 HOW TO ADD THE SCHEMA OF THE DATA

Adding the application schema language for the data can also be done by linking the citation title with an anchor. Unfortunately, the title is not shown in the GeoNetwork visualization interface for some unknown reason, so we had to add an alternative title with the same information to make it also visible in the presentation. The initial purpose of the schema information is to validate the data structure in distribution info but it can also be used to communicate the data fields structure in a format such as a CSVW⁴³ or JSON Schema⁴⁴. In this case, we use one of the attached files as a URL instead of an external resource (Figure 32 and Figure 33).

```

<gmd:applicationSchemaInfo>
  <gmd:MD_ApplicationSchemaInformation>
    <gmd:name>
      <gmd:CI_Citation>
        <gmd:title>
          <gmx:Anchor xlink:href="
https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/63a296c5-f132-4174-bac5-babe5ad94f2a/attach
ments/GBIF_Mammals_ANSI_csw.txt">Mammals occurrences GBIF test schema</gmx:Anchor>
          </gmd:title>
          <gmd:alternateTitle>
            <gmx:Anchor xlink:href="
https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/63a296c5-f132-4174-bac5-babe5ad94f2a/attach
ments/GBIF_Mammals_ANSI_csw.txt">Mammals occurrences GBIF test schema</gmx:Anchor>
            </gmd:alternateTitle>
          <gmd:date>
            <gmd:CI_Date/>
          </gmd:CI_Citation>
        </gmd:name>
      <gmd:schemaLanguage>
        <gco:CharacterString>JSON</gco:CharacterString>
      </gmd:schemaLanguage>
      <gmd:constraintLanguage>
        <gco:CharacterString>CSVW</gco:CharacterString>
      </gmd:constraintLanguage>
    </gmd:MD_ApplicationSchemaInformation>
  </gmd:applicationSchemaInfo>
  
```

Figure 32 XML fragment to show the addition to the schema of the data using the citation title.

⁴³ <https://csvw.org/>

⁴⁴ <https://json-schema.org/>

Figure 33 Schema of the data information as it is presented in the GeoNetwork GUI.

The exemplified XML file is published at:

<https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/63a296c5-f132-4174-bac5-babe5ad94f2a/formatters/xml?approved=true>

3.2.2.4 HOW TO EXPRESS QUALITY WITH QUALITYML AND UNCERTML

QualityML⁴⁵ is a profile of the ISO (e.g. ISO 19115 and ISO 19157) providing a set of rules for precisely documenting quality information as well as vocabularies for concepts in a linked data style. These vocabularies encompass quality indicators, quality measures, quality domains and matrices. Quality matrices use statistic expressions for describing uncertainties, whenever possible, from the UncertML⁴⁶ dictionary. In addition, the QualityML documentation provides a set of examples on how to encode data quality in ISO 19115/19139XML (with and without extending the ISO metadata)⁴⁷ that are used as a reference in AD4GD. An example using QualityML vocabularies and metrics in an ISO metadata is presented in Figure 34.

⁴⁵ <https://www.qualityml.org/>

⁴⁶ <http://www.uncertml.org>

⁴⁷ <https://www.qualityml.org/#xmlencoding>

```

<gmd:dataQualityInfo>
  <gmd:DQ_DataQuality>
    <gmd:scope>
    <gmd:report>
      <gmd:DQ_AbsoluteExternalPositionalAccuracy>
        <gmd:nameOfMeasure>
          <gco:CharacterString>Bias of positions</gco:CharacterString>
        </gmd:nameOfMeasure>
        <gmd:measureIdentification>
          <gmd:RS_Identifier>
            <gmd:code>
              <gmx:Anchor xlink:href="
https://www.qualityml.org/1.0/measure/BiasOfPositions?domain=DifferentialErrors2D">Position bias, 2D differential error
measure</gmx:Anchor>
            </gmd:code>
            <gmd:codeSpace>
              <gco:CharacterString>https://www.qualityml.org/1.0/measure</gco:CharacterString>
            </gmd:codeSpace>
          </gmd:RS_Identifier>
          <gmd:measureDescription>
            <gco:CharacterString>Bias of the positions for a set of positions where the positional uncertainties are defined
as the deviation between a measured position and what is considered as the corresponding true position.</
gco:CharacterString>
          </gmd:measureDescription>
          <gmd:result>
            <gmd:DQ_QuantitativeResult>
              <gmd:valueType>
                <gco:RecordType>Double precision real</gco:RecordType>
              </gmd:valueType>
              <gmd:valueUnit xlink:href="https://www.isotc211.org/2005/resources/uom/ML_gmxUom.xml#m"/>
              <gmd:errorStatistic>
                <gmx:Anchor xlink:href="https://www.qualityml.org/1.0/metrics/MeanBias">Mean Bias</gmx:Anchor>
              </gmd:errorStatistic>
              <gmd:value>
                <gco:Record>Depending of each point</gco:Record>
              </gmd:value>
            </gmd:DQ_QuantitativeResult>
          </gmd:result>
        </gmd:DQ_AbsoluteExternalPositionalAccuracy>
      </gmd:report>
    <gmd:lineage>
  </gmd:DQ_DataQuality>
</gmd:dataQualityInfo>

```

Figure 34 QualityML vocabularies and metrics in an ISO metadata file.

The same result in GeoNetwork is presented in Figure 35.

Figure 35 QualityML vocabularies and metrics as in GeoNetwork GUI.

The complete XML file is published at:

<https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/63a296c5-f132-4174-bac5-babe5ad94f2a/formatters/xml?approved=true>

3.2.2.5 MINIMAL METADATA TO DOCUMENT

The ISO 19115:2003 defines an extensive set of elements to describe a geographic dataset in detail. However, to be compliant with the standard only a subset of elements – known as core metadata- is required. These elements are classified as Mandatory (M), Optional (O), and conditional (C - meaning they are mandatory under certain conditions). While the mandatory elements ensure basic compliance with the standard, ISO authors recommend including optional ones to increase interoperability. Table 1 lists the ISO 19115 core metadata elements and specifies the information that AD4GD should document for geographic datasets.

Name	Domain	Obligation	AD4GD metadata
Dataset title	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.title	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Dataset reference date	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.date	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Dataset responsible party	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.pointOfContact > CI_ResponsibleParty	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Geographic location of the dataset	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.extent > EX_Extent > EX_GeographicExtent = EX_GeographicBoundingBox or EX_GeographicDescription	Conditional (C)	Yes
Dataset language	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.language	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Dataset character set	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.characterSet	Conditional (C)	Yes

Name	Domain	Obligation	AD4GD metadata
Dataset topic category	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.topicCategory	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Spatial resolution of the dataset	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.spatialResolution > MD_Resolution.equivalentScale or MD_Resolution.distance	Optional (C)	If possible
Abstract describing the dataset	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.abstract	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Distribution format	MD_Metadata > MD_Distribution > MD_Format.name and MD_Format.version	Optional (C)	Yes
Additional extent information for the dataset	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.extent > EX_Extent > EX_TemporalExtent or EX_VerticalExtent	Optional (C)	Yes
Spatial representation type	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.spatialRepresentation Type	Optional (C)	Yes
Reference system	MD_Metadata > MD_ReferenceSystem	Optional (C)	Yes
Lineage	MD_Metadata > DQ_DataQuality.lineage > LI_Lineage	Optional (C)	If possible
On-line resource	MD_Metadata > MD_Distribution > MD_DigitalTransferOption.onLine > CI_OnlineResource	Optional (C)	If possible
Metadata file identifier	MD_Metadata.fileIdentifier	Optional (C)	Yes
Metadata standard name	MD_Metadata.metadataStandardName	Optional (C)	Yes
Metadata standard version	MD_Metadata.metadataStandardVersion	Optional (C)	Yes
Metadata language	MD_Metadata.language	Conditional (C)	Yes
Metadata character set	MD_Metadata.characterSet	Conditional (C)	Yes
Metadata point of contact	MD_Metadata.contact > CI_ResponsibleParty	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Metadata date stamp	MD_Metadata.dateStamp	Mandatory (M)	Yes

Table 1 ISO 19115 core metadata elements used in AD4GD to document geographic datasets.

As can be appreciated in the previous Table 1, in AD4GD we are targeting to document most of the core metadata with special focus on *on-line resource*. In a dataspace focused on data exchange of information, only metadata records that are directly related to the actual data in the dataspace are acceptable. For example, the TAPIS tool (Section 3.3.2.2), when reading metadata for a catalogue, discards any record not linked to the dataset with an *on-line resource*. About the Lineage information (provenance including processes and sources), this is considered a very important topic for data trust and data quality, in dataspace. Unfortunately, the *Lineage* model in ISO19115 is considered incomplete. There is discussion on AD4GD on upgrading to ISO 19115-1 as this is considered the main improvement between 19115 and 19115-1. The concept of *Spatial resolution* is often problematic in AD4GD for in-situ observations as it is not so easy to determine when referring to a dataset composed by a few in-situ measurements captured in an irregular distribution over time.

3.2.2.6 PUBLIC METADATA AND PRIVATE METADATA

GeoNetwork allows for public and private metadata records. A common practice in mapping agencies or other organizations that manage large geographical databases is to keep metadata records private until they are considered completely documented and validated for publication according to a predefined

criterion. In AD4GD the protocol for assessing when a metadata record should be published consists in two quality checks:

- Metadata information is complete according to the minimal metadata to document (see the previous subsection)
- The XML files is valid according to the XML schema.

This procedure is done by CREAM under its role of administration of the GeoNetwork catalogue which also includes the task of ensuring the quality of the metadata records produced AD4GD.

3.3 CONNECTING GEONETWORK WITH OTHER TECHNICAL COMPONENTS

GeoNetwork environment allows for harvesting and synchronization of metadata between distributed catalogues and with external services. The services selected by AD4GD project to develop the case studies are presented below.

3.3.1 ACCESSING GEONETWORK VIA OGC CSW

The Open Geospatial Catalogue Service for the Web (OGC-CSW)⁴⁸ allows to query, update and the insertion of metadata records through HTTP requests. GeoNetwork supports retrieving metadata at least in ISO 19115/19139 and DCAT standards. The following requests can be used to retrieve the full AD4GD GeoNetwork catalogue as ISO19115:2003 or as DCAT:

- As ISO19115:2003:

[https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=gmd:MD_Metadata&namespace=xmlns\(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd\)&outputSchema=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full](https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=gmd:MD_Metadata&namespace=xmlns(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd)&outputSchema=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full)

- As DCAT:

[https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=dcat&namespace=xmlns\(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd\)&outputSchema=http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat%23&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full](https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=dcat&namespace=xmlns(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd)&outputSchema=http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat%23&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full)

While requesting a subset of the metadata records is possible, due to the modest volume of the number of datasets produced by AD4GD pilots, this possibility was considered unnecessary.

3.3.2 CONNECTING WITH THE REST OF THE DATASPACE

3.3.2.1 CONNECTING GEONETWORK WITH OGC STA/STAPLUS

As exposed in detail in previous deliverables (e.g., AD4GD D6.1 Pilot Technical Implementation Planning, Implementation and Assessment⁴⁹, AD4GD D3.1 Heterogeneous IoT Data Integration Model⁵⁰) the OGC SensorThings API (STA)⁵¹/STApplus⁵² are the open standards selected by AD4GD to discover sensor data and make it accessible in the GDDS.

The sensor data used and produced in the framework of the project pilots (Pilot 1: Water Quality, Pilot 2: Biodiversity, Pilot 3: Air Quality) is distributed via an STApplus service (hosted in the IoT Lab FROST server

⁴⁸ <https://docs.ogc.org/is/12-168r6/12-168r6.html>

⁴⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/10839023>

⁵⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/13757222>

⁵¹ <https://www.ogc.org/publications/standard/sensorthings/>

⁵² <https://www.ogc.org/es/publications/standard/sensor-things-api-extension/>

(and documented in GeoNetwork metadata catalogue)). Figure 36 **STApplus data model**. shows the STApplus data model.

Figure 36 STApplus data model.

To connect GeoNetwork with STApplus datastreams, the approach consists of using the ISO 19115 **MD_Distribution** information (see Figure 24) in the metadata to link against a filter or filters of observations related STApplus datastream. As an example, the following links refer to three different datastreams describing different subsets of a dataset containing camera trap observations related in STApplus that has been included as three distribution information in the metadata (including (1) a link to the species occurrences, (2) a link to the species pictures, and (3) a link combining both information):

1. [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties\(58\)/Datastreams\(35\)/Observations?\\$expand=Datastream\(\\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\\$expand=ObservedProperty\(\\$select=definition\)\)&FeatureOfInterest\(\\$select=feature\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(58)/Datastreams(35)/Observations?$expand=Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition))&FeatureOfInterest($select=feature))
2. [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties\(59\)/Datastreams\(36\)/Observations?\\$expand=Datastream\(\\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\\$expand=ObservedProperty\(\\$select=definition\)\)&FeatureOfInterest\(\\$select=feature\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(59)/Datastreams(36)/Observations?$expand=Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition))&FeatureOfInterest($select=feature))
3. [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties\(58\)/Datastreams\(35\)/Observations?\\$expand=ObservationGroups\(\\$expand=Observations\),Datastream\(\\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\\$expand=ObservedProperty\(\\$select=definition\)\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(58)/Datastreams(35)/Observations?$expand=ObservationGroups($expand=Observations),Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition)))

(Please note that a login to FROST server is required to access the data behind these links).

The XML fragment showing the MD_Distribution information to connect with STApplus is shown in Figure 37.

```

<gmd:transferOptions>
  <gmd:MD_DigitalTransferOptions>
    <gmd:onLine>
      <gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
        <gmd:linkage>
          <gmd:URL>https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(58)/Datastreams(35)/Observations?
            $expand=Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition)),FeatureOfInterest($select=feature)</gmd:URL>
          </gmd:linkage>
        <gmd:protocol>
          <gco:CharacterString>OGC:SOS-1.0.0-http-get-observation</gco:CharacterString>
          </gmd:protocol>
        <gmd:name>
          <gco:CharacterString>Occurrences</gco:CharacterString>
          </gmd:name>
        </gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
      </gmd:onLine>
    </gmd:onLine>
    <gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
      <gmd:linkage>
          <gmd:URL>https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(59)/Datastreams(36)/Observations?
            $expand=Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition)),FeatureOfInterest($select=feature)</gmd:URL>
          </gmd:linkage>
        <gmd:protocol>
          <gco:CharacterString>OGC:SOS-1.0.0-http-get-observation</gco:CharacterString>
          </gmd:protocol>
        <gmd:name>
          <gco:CharacterString>Pictures of camera trap</gco:CharacterString>
          </gmd:name>
        <gmd:description>
          <gco:CharacterString>Pictures of wild animals</gco:CharacterString>
          </gmd:description>
        </gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
      </gmd:onLine>
    </gmd:onLine>
    <gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
      <gmd:linkage>
          <gmd:URL>https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(58)/Datastreams(35)/Observations?
            $expand=ObservationGroups($expand=Observations),Datastream($select=unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty($select=definition))
          </gmd:URL>
          </gmd:linkage>
        <gmd:protocol>
          <gco:CharacterString>OGC:SOS-1.0.0-http-get-observation</gco:CharacterString>
          </gmd:protocol>
        <gmd:name>
          <gco:CharacterString>Occurrences with pictures</gco:CharacterString>
          </gmd:name>
        </gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
      </gmd:onLine>
    </gmd:CI_OnlineResource>
  </gmd:MD_DigitalTransferOptions>
</gmd:transferOptions>
</gmd:MD_Distribution>
</gmd:distributionInfo>
</gmd:MD_Metadata>

```

Figure 37 XML fragment showing the MD_Distribution information to connect with STApplus.

The complete XML file is published at:

<https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/73a4ad42-63da-40e3-9658-04218db67279/formatters/xml?approved=true>

3.3.2.2 CONNECTING GEONETWORK WITH TAPIS

TAPIS (Tables from OGC APIs for Sensors)⁵³ is a client application developed in HTML and JavaScript to support mobilisation to STApplus in a GUI as well as to access OGC API features and CSW. It can also open local files (e.g. CSV and GeoJSON) and allows semantic annotation of data as tables. In other words, TAPIS acts as an STApplus data Explorer and CSV tables can be imported into a STApplus server automatically and vice versa.

From TAPIS, it is possible to connect to a catalogue of metadata using the OGC CSW standard. Every record in the CSW becomes one or more rows in a table. Then it is possible to select a CSV dataset (if available as Online resource in a CSW record) and present it also as a table. Figure 38 exemplifies how to connect TAPIS to the GeoNetwork AD4GD catalogue.

⁵³ <https://www.tapis.grumets.cat/>

Figure 38 TAPIS connection to the GeoNetwork AD4GD catalogue.

The result is a table with a list of all records in the catalogue that have data (Online resources) associated with it (Figure 39).

OGC query URL: <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&elementSetName=full&typeName=>

Show row numbers Show self and navigation links

	id	title	dataURL
1	9c318b30-0d8f-4553-bc4c-0b5d28eecdfe	Surface water conductivity in river Spree, 2016	https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/sr/api/records/9c318b30-0d8f-4553-bc4c-0b5d28eecdfe/attachments/Wald_Aqua100Data.csv
2	95b1008-d73d-4082-9572-0c471b6f5ead	Interaction Flow (IF) index	https://sourcesup.renater.fr/www/graphab/en/home.html
3	dc3b6286-8c52-4fee-947f-c495dc03c75c	Terrestrial Connectivity Index (ICT)	https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdo.py/collections/TerrestrialConnectivityIndex/coverage
4	dc3b6286-8c52-4fee-947f-c495dc03c75c	Terrestrial Connectivity Index (ICT)	https://www.datacube.cat/BioConn/ICT/
5	0a13b5c9-1fde-3625-bd82-4a37b09e9e24	Gewässerkarte	https://fbinter.stadt-berlin.de/fb/feed/senstadt/a_gewkarte
6	0a13b5c9-1fde-3625-bd82-4a37b09e9e24	Gewässerkarte	https://fbinter.stadt-berlin.de/fb/feed/senstadt/a_gewkarte/0
7	0a13b5c9-1fde-3625-bd82-4a37b09e9e24	Gewässerkarte	https://fbinter.stadt-berlin.de/fb/index.jsp?loginkey=showMap&mapid=gewkarte@senstadt
8	a110782b-b213-4922-988a-8778a90f8b9d	Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia - 2022	https://agricultura.gencat.cat/ca/servis/cartografia-sig/bases-cartografiques/usos-sol-subsol/usos-sol/
9	73a4ad42-83da-40e3-9658-04218db07279	Camera trap pictures and occurrences	https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(56)/Datastreams(35)/Observations? \$expand=Datastream(\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\$expand=ObservedProperty(\$select=definition))&FeatureOfInterest(\$select=feature)
10	73a4ad42-83da-40e3-9658-04218db07279	Camera trap pictures and occurrences	https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(59)/Datastreams(36)/Observations? \$expand=Datastream(\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\$expand=ObservedProperty(\$select=definition))&FeatureOfInterest(\$select=feature)
11	73a4ad42-83da-40e3-9658-04218db07279	Camera trap pictures and occurrences	https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings2/v1.1/ObservedProperties(56)/Datastreams(35)/Observations? \$expand=ObservationGroups(\$expand=Observations).Datastream(\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\$expand=ObservedProperty(\$select=definition))
12	63a296c5-f132-4174-bac5-babe5ad94f2a	Mammals occurrences GBIF test	https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/63a296c5-f132-4174-bac5-babe5ad94f2a/attachments/GBIF_Mammals_ANSI.csv
13	fa2987e-59ab-4cde-a8ff-8fa62c78bc07_TMP0002T	Water Level Krumme Lanke Berlin	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php

Figure 39 List of all records in the GeoNetwork AD4GD catalogue that have data associated with it.

Depending on the format, it is possible to immediately open the resource without having to write the URL of the resource. In this case we use the [ImportCSV] functionality to open a CSV file. The related table can be examined and analysed, and information can be statistically aggregated and summarized as well as represented as charts.

This process is explained step-by-step as part of TAPIS documentation, at: <https://www.tapis.grumets.cat/help/#recipe07>

3.3.2.3 GEONETWORK RELATIONSHIP WITH THE DSSC CATALOGUE CONCEPT

AD4GD has adopted the **Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC)**⁵⁴ building blocks to establish the elements required to support the implementation of the GDDS. The specifications for the technical building blocks consist of the following elements: Data Models; Data Exchange; Provenance and Traceability; Access and Usage policies and control; Identity Management; Trust; Data, Services and Offerings descriptions; Publication and Discovery; Marketplaces.

The Publication and Discovery building block addresses the “Data, Services & Offerings Catalogue” and the generic catalogue functionality (Figure 40).

⁵⁴ <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE/357073899/Building+Block+Overview>

Figure 40 DSSC Catalogue and Publication and Discovery components (extracted from: <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE/357076320/Publication+and+Discovery>)

The DSSC recommends the catalogue protocol specification initiated by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) for data sharing in a dataspace. In the context of the dataspace protocol, a catalogue is a collection of data offerings published by a data product provider in the form of DCAT standard datasets and data services using the DCAT:Catalog class and its properties⁵⁵. Thus, as GeoNetwork supports the DCAT standard, it should not be difficult to adapt the proposed AD4GD implementation to be compatible with the DSSC concept.

As already exemplified in Section 3.3.1, the following request can be used to retrieve via an OGC CSW the full AD4GD GeoNetwork catalogue as DCAT:

[https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=dcat&namespace=xmlns\(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd\)&outputSchema=http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat%23&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full](https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=dcat&namespace=xmlns(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd)&outputSchema=http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat%23&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full)

In the months to come we will experiment with the Eclipse Dataspace Connector and conduct interoperability experiments with the catalogue implementation that it incorporates, comparing it with the response of AD4GD GeoNetwork and propose recommendations for harmonization between the two catalogues.

⁵⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Catalog>

4 DATA TRUSTWORTHINESS FRAMEWORK

This section deals with Component 11, task 4.4. It describes a developing methodology for assessing and describing the trustworthiness of datasets consumed and produced by AD4GD. We will examine the aspects of data trustworthiness that have been raised by each pilot project and integrate them into a data trustworthiness framework. The data trustworthiness framework is the component 11 within the AD4GD list of components. As the development of this framework is an ongoing process, a living document outlining the framework will be maintained within the AD4GD GitHub repository⁵⁶.

Many of the individual technical and procedural components necessary for this are already present, having been described in the previous sections and in previous deliverables. Particularly relevant will be the description of our data catalogue and the use of the ISO19115 model in Section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**: Data Catalogue and Metadata, which will frequently refer from here. The aim of this section is to bring these components together into a framework that can be applied in a reproducible manner.

4.1 CONTRIBUTIONS TO TRUSTWORTHINESS

Name	Description
Completeness	Presence and absence of features, their attributes and their relationships.
Logical consistency	Degree of adherence to logical rules of data structure, attribution and relationships (data structure can be conceptual, logical or physical).
Positional accuracy	Accuracy of the position of features within a spatial reference system.
Temporal quality	Accuracy of the temporal attributes and temporal relationships of features.
Thematic accuracy	Accuracy of quantitative attributes and the correctness of non-quantitative attributes and of the classifications of features and their relationships.
Usability	Degree of adherence of a dataset to a specific set of requirements. Usability is based on user requirements. All quality elements may be used to evaluate usability.
Metaquality	Metaquality elements are a set of quantitative and qualitative statements about a quality evaluation and its result.
Certainty	Information certainty elements are a set of qualitative statements to communicate the degree of confidence/likelihood of the findings of a simulation, prediction or indicator.

Table 2 The Quality classes defined by QualityML. ⁵⁷

In Section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, we discussed the representation of metadata. In short, we will use the ISO19115:2003 metadata model with GeoNetwork as the data catalogue system⁵⁸.

⁵⁶ <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-Data-Trustworthiness-Framework>

⁵⁷ Retrieved from <https://www.qualityml.org/> 30/10/2024

⁵⁸ Hereafter, ISO 19115:2003 will be referred to simply as ISO 19115 but be aware that many other versions exist.

GeoNetwork provides the user interface to create and browse catalogue entries that conform to ISO 19115:2003. We will link terms, units and definitions that we use in our XML records to the semantic URLs being defined in WP3 and hosted on the RAINBOW server. This is done by replacing text fields (`gco:CharacterString`) with `<gmx:anchor>` tags that contain both the text and a URI link to semantic concepts.

Finally, we discuss QualityML⁵⁹, a profile of ISO 19115 and ISO 19157 that provides rules for documenting quality information, including vocabulary terms. This allows for a standardised way to record statistical quantities and units of measure. Table 2 shows the quality classes defined by QualityML (see Section 3). These classes provide us a framework for what axes of quality and trustworthiness information we can be provided in our metadata records. They cover both quantitative and qualitative measures.

QualityML also provides URIs for each measure, domain, and metric, which can be used to make quality metadata interoperable. By encoding quality information with these URIs, we can integrate and share quality descriptions on GeoNetwork.

To create and populate these metadata records, we will also need methods to discover or assess the quality and trustworthiness of datasets. Those that are most relevant to the datasets within AD4GD are:

- **Groundtruthing:** Comparison against known trustworthy datasets.
- **Data lineage (or provenance):** The sources and process steps used to create the dataset.
- **External or propagated uncertainty:** External uncertainty information can be derived from sensor calibration or modelling. Propagated uncertainty is derived from uncertainty propagation methods.
- **Published Research:** Information from peer reviewed studies that examine the dataset or methodology.
- **Geospatial User Feedback:** Feedback from end users of the dataset.

The degree to which each of these is relevant or applicable varies between datasets. The datasets produced and consumed across each of the three pilots in the project will be analysed along each of the above axes. From these, we will build up a set of recommendations that will form the basis of the data trustworthiness framework.

Finally, there is the question of the granularity of metadata. So far, we have discussed attaching metadata records to datasets. However, there may be instances where we want to provide more fine-grained information such as quality scores for individual sensors or even for individual observations. At this granularity level, alternative standards such as OGC SensorThings API⁶⁰ become relevant. We will see examples of this in Pilot 3: Air Quality.

In what follows, we will examine each of these potential sources of trustworthiness information.

4.1.1 GROUNDTRUTHING AND OBSERVATION OPERATORS

In the simplest case, groundtruthing a dataset means directly comparing it against another more reliable dataset. The groundtruth dataset is itself unsuitable for the intended application, perhaps because it has a limited domain, is too sparse or only measures a subset of the observables of interest. To the extent that the dataset of interest diverges from the groundtruth we can collect quantitative and qualitative information about the degree of divergence and hence establish a chain of trustworthiness.

⁵⁹ <https://www.qualityml.org/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.ogc.org/publications/standard/sensorthings/>

Often, the data and the groundtruth datasets will measure different but related quantities. Observation operators can be defined that map between these datasets. Observations operators will form a useful conceptual part of our groundtruthing framework.

For example, the output of a numerical weather model can be groundtruthed against satellite observational data. However, satellites measure spectral properties of the Earth as viewed from above while weather models estimate quantities such as pressure and temperature over three-dimensional domains. Here the observation operator combines three operations:

1. Interpolating from the weather model grid onto the pixel grid of the satellite image.
2. Collapsing the three-dimensional column of the atmosphere into a flat pixel as viewed from space.
3. Transforming between the variables dealt with by the weather model and those contained in satellite imagery.

In what follows, we will discuss generalised observation operators as they apply to the datasets used in AD4GD.

4.1.2 LINEAGE SOURCES AND PROCESS STEPS

While groundtruthing allows the creation of a chain of trust through direct data comparisons, another chain of trust can be formed by examining the lineage of a dataset: that is the tree of source datasets and processes from which a particular dataset has been computed. If trust is established in each source dataset and process step used to generate a target dataset, then a high degree of confidence can be established in the final dataset.

Proper documentation of these process steps allows users to trace the sources of data, understand how the data has been processed, and identify any potential sources of uncertainty or bias introduced during those processes. For example, in geospatial datasets, this could involve tracking satellite data from its raw collection through various processing steps such as atmospheric correction, georeferencing, and integration with other data sources, such as ground-based sensors.

Furthermore, lineage plays an important role in data integration. When datasets from different sources are combined, the lineage of each dataset should be tracked to ensure compatibility and reliability. For instance, in a multi-source data scenario, such as combining IoT sensor data with weather model outputs, it is important to have a clear record of how the data was rescaled, corrected, or interpolated to harmonize it with other sources. These transformation steps should be fully transparent to allow users to assess the impact of each process on the final output.

In ISO 19115, it is possible to attach CI_Citation elements to process steps within the dataset's lineage information, allowing for detailed documentation of the sources or scholarly references that support or describe specific steps in the data creation process. This is typically done through the LI_Lineage and LI_ProcessStep classes. Each LI_ProcessStep can include a citation element (**Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**), allowing a CI_Citation to be linked directly to that specific step.

```

<gmd:lineage>
  <gmd:LI_Lineage>
    <gmd:processStep>
      <gmd:LI_ProcessStep>
        <gmd:description>
          <gco:CharacterString>
            Atmospheric correction was applied to raw satellite
            imagery to remove the effects of atmospheric interference, enhancing surface
            reflectance accuracy.
          </gco:CharacterString>
        </gmd:description>
        <gmd:dateTime>
          <gco:DateTime>2023-06-15T10:30:00</gco:DateTime>
        </gmd:dateTime>
        <gmd:citation>
          <gmd:CI_Citation>
            <gmd:title>
              <gco:CharacterString>Methodology for Atmospheric
              Correction of Satellite Imagery</gco:CharacterString>
            </gmd:title>
            ... More XML ...
          </gmd:CI_Citation>
        </gmd:citation>
      </gmd:LI_ProcessStep>
    </gmd:processStep>
  </gmd:LI_Lineage>
</gmd:lineage>

```

Figure 41 A truncated LI_Lineage showing how CI_Citation may be embedded into process steps.

4.1.3 EXTERNAL OR PROPAGATED UNCERTAINTY

External sources of uncertainty information can play a critical role in assessing the trustworthiness of a dataset, particularly when uncertainties are not inherent to the data but arise from external factors such as sensor calibration errors, environmental conditions during data collection, or limitations in the modelling assumptions used to generate the data. These uncertainties can be quantified using statistical methods or derived from empirical studies and calibration processes. When datasets are processed or combined, these uncertainties may be carefully propagated to compute an estimate of the uncertainty in the final output.

This propagation can involve techniques such as algebraic uncertainty propagation, Monte Carlo simulation, or sensitivity analysis, which allow for a systematic transfer of uncertainty from the input data through various computational stages into the output data.

4.1.4 PUBLISHED RESEARCH

Peer reviewed research is often an important source for the information already discussed. This may include entire datasets, model parameters or assumptions, the results of ground truthing existing datasets and assessments of the validity of measurements techniques and process steps.

In the ISO 19115 metadata standard, links to published research can be represented using citation elements. The CI_Citation class in ISO 19115 allows for the inclusion of standard bibliographic information, such as title, date, and author, as well as the addition of online resource attributes to link directly to digital versions of research articles or unique identifiers like DOIs, enabling robust referencing and traceability. By linking datasets to authoritative research, ISO 19115 metadata enhances the transparency and trustworthiness of the dataset, as users can access relevant scientific studies to better understand the dataset's context, methodology, and limitations. This structure supports the establishment of a chain of trust by embedding scholarly resources directly within the dataset's metadata.

4.1.5 FEEDBACK FROM END USERS: GEOSPATIAL USER FEEDBACK

Geospatial User Feedback (GUF) defines a data model for recording feedback from data consumers as they use the datasets. This is in addition to other metadata which is typically generated by the creator, publisher or curator of a dataset. GUF reuses some elements of ISO 19115-1:2014 but doesn't inherit the general structure.

GUF provides elements for:

- Commenting, asking questions and providing answers (GUF_UserComment)
- Rating data (GUF_Rating)
- Citing publications (QCM_Publication)
- Providing additional quality measures (additionalQuality)
- Additional lineage information (additional LineageSteps)
- Emphasizing a significant event that conditions the interpretation of a dataset (GUF_SignificantEvent)

GUF also extends some of the elements defined by ISO 19115-1:2014 such as CI_Citation .

Within AD4GD we will test GUF as a framework for collecting user feedback on the datasets we generate as a part of the project as part of T6.4.

4.1.6 SUMMARY

This section has outlined a data trustworthiness framework for datasets used and generated by AD4GD, focusing on factors such as ground truthing, data lineage, uncertainty propagation, published research, and user feedback. In what follows we will examine each pilot project in turn through the lens of this framework.

The pilot projects are described in detail in other deliverables, particularly D6.1, hence we will only briefly introduce each pilot project before looking at which elements of the data trustworthiness framework are relevant.

4.2 PILOT 1: WATER QUALITY

Figure 42 Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 1.

Pilot 1 focuses on developing tools and indices to monitor and improve the management of small urban lakes⁶¹, which play vital ecological and recreational roles but are often neglected in traditional water monitoring frameworks. Due to Berlin's rapid urbanization and climate change, these lakes face increasing challenges from pollution, nutrient loads, and water scarcity, exacerbated by stormwater runoff and fluctuating groundwater influence. The pilot aims to create a Water Quality Index (WQI) and Water Availability Index (WAI) by combining data from satellite observations, IoT sensors, and Citizen Science inputs with AI-driven analytics. These indices will help stakeholders –ranging from city officials to citizens– prioritize interventions, monitor long-term trends, and make informed decisions to support sustainable lake ecosystems. The goal is to provide a scalable solution that can enhance water management in Berlin and be transferred to similar urban environments.

⁶¹ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-1>

Name	Source	Input/Output
	Was this data created within AD4GD?	How does this data fit into the dataflow of the pilot?
Satellite Data: Harmonized Sentinel-2 MSI ⁶²	External	Input
Citizen Science Data	External	Input
Berlin Senate "Wasserportal" ⁶³	External	Input
Berlin Senate "FIS-Broker"	External	Input
KWB IoT Data	AD4GD	Input
KWB Lab Data	AD4GD	Input
German Weather Forecast and Historic Data	External	Input
Satellite Derived Trophic Indices	AD4GD	Intermediate
Water Quality Regression Model	AD4GD	Intermediate
Water Quality Index	AD4GD	Output
Water Availability Index	AD4GD	Output

Table 3 Datasets in use in Pilot 1

On a technical level, pilot 1 will work in two stages. In the first stage, observational data such as weather and satellite data are combined with ground truth measures of lake water quality to create a prediction model. In the second stage, a user interface allows the user to create different scenarios such as dry spells or severe rain. The prediction model is then used to produce forecasts for how a given scenario would impact lake water quality.

4.2.1 DATASET TRUSTWORTHINESS

Looking at the input datasets in turn.

Sentinel 2 Satellite Imagery. While Sentinel 2 datasets are highly documented and quality assessed⁶⁴, some sentinel 2 products have been documented with ISO 19115-2 and extensions⁶⁵, but not all have. This highlights the difficulty of importing metadata from external datasets which may be partial or based on different standards than those in use internally. In this case we will link to external sources of trustworthiness information when documenting this dataset on GeoNetwork.

German Weather Forecast and Historical Weather data. This includes quantities like precipitation, evaporation, wind speed, solar irradiance and air temperature. These datasets come with extensive quality and calibration information. The key limitation that the data have in pilot 1 is their limited spatial

⁶² <https://sentiwiki.copernicus.eu/web/sentinel-2>

⁶³ <https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php>

⁶⁴ https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/349490/S2_MSI_Product_Specification.pdf

⁶⁵ <https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/documents/247904/3119978/Sentinel-5P-L01B-metadata-specifications>

resolution, sometimes covering a lake with only one or two grid cells. This highlights that quality and trustworthiness are highly use case dependent measures.

Berlin Senate “Wasserportal” water quality indicators. This dataset consists of a single yearly trophic state measurement for each of 294 lakes in Brandenburg over a 5-year span. The dataset comes with very little external quality information. We do assign to it a degree of trust because of the direct method of data collection, in contrast to the remote sensing methods which are also used.

Citizen Science Data. These datasets consist of manual measurements of water quality collected by volunteers. This includes using test strips to measure nutrient levels, low cost conductivity and pH sensors, and qualitative information entered into a smartphone app. These measurements include uncertainties that come from sources such as variation in the location and depth of water samples, differing interpretations of the colour of the test strips and the inherent variation in qualitative measurements taken by multiple individual volunteers. This data could benefit from QualityML’s **Non-Quantitative Attribute Accuracy** (for subjective measures) and **Completeness** to capture potential biases, variances, and missing data due to volunteer-based sampling.

IoT data collected by KWB. Continuous measurements taken with low cost IoT sensors deployed by KWB. As is often the case with low cost IoT sensors, there is little calibration or uncertainty information available for these sensors.

Both the IoT data and the Citizen science data will be ground truthed against the “Wasserportal” data to derive quality information.

Trophic Indices: Centroid Reflection Wavelength (CRW). A water quality index, CRW, is being developed that will predict water quality directly from multispectral satellite imagery. This model will be ground truthed against the direct water quality measurements such as the “Wasserportal”, IoT and citizen science data.

User Feedback. Splashboard will incorporate user feedback on datasets using the GUF model.

4.2.2 CALIBRATION AND GROUND TRUTHING

Figure 43 and Figure 44 show the results of ground truthing CRW against the Berlin Senate “Wasserportal” water quality indicators. Statistical measures based on these results will be incorporated into the final metadata record on GeoNetwork.

Figure 43 A regression of the Centroid Reflection Wavelength against Trophic indices from the Wasserportal data showing good agreement between the two.

Figure 44 A Confusion matrix showing how often Centroid Wavelength estimates of lake trophic state agree with ground truth data from Wasserportal. The diagonal green line indicates cases where the two datasets.

4.3 PILOT 2: BIODIVERSITY

Figure 45 Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 2.

Pilot 2⁶⁶ focuses on advancing biodiversity conservation by evaluating functional landscape connectivity (FLC) in Catalonia, Spain. Recognizing the significance of ecological connectivity for species migration and healthy ecosystems, this pilot aligns with global and European biodiversity strategies, including the European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. It aims to provide scalable, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data tools to assess and enhance landscape connectivity, supporting informed decision-making among stakeholders, from policymakers to local biodiversity initiatives. To achieve this, Pilot 2 integrates satellite, administrative, and Citizen Science data with analysis to deliver actionable insights into ecological corridors and species movement.

⁶⁶ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2>

Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. shows a simplified data flow diagram for Pilot 2. As with Pilot 1, the technical and scientific details of Pilot 2 are laid out in detail in D6.1 but we will provide a summary here. Outside of AD4GD, raw satellite imagery is used to infer Land Use Land Cover (LULC) maps for the region of interest. LULC maps segment the area of interest into a set of regions labelled with land use categories.

Within the project these LULC maps are preprocessed, adding in fine details on features that could affect habitat connectivity such as roads and railways. This step uses Open Street Map data. In addition, during preprocessing, protected areas from the World Database on Protected areas are integrated to consider their importance for connecting habitats. The output of this steps is an enriched LULC map. Next, these enriched LULC maps are used to compute habitat connectivity. At this point there are multiple methods that are applicable, such as Graphab⁶⁷, which applies a graph-based methodology for computing connectivity and MiraMon⁶⁸, which uses a grid based method. Finally, ATOS is working on a machine learning based approach that would be trained based on MiraMon with the aim to be substantially more resource efficient.

Implicitly, expert knowledge and model parameters from published literature have been incorporated during both the preprocessing and modelling steps, this will be accounted for in the resulting metadata.

Name	Source	Input/Output
Pilot 1	Was this data created within AD4GD?	How does this data fit into the dataflow of the pilot?
Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia	External	Input
Open Street Map (OSM) data	External	Input
Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia, enriched with OSM	AD4GD	Intermediate
Camera Trap Data	AD4GD	Input
UKCEH (UK level land cover map) produced by Center for Ecology and Hydrology	External	Input
World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA)	External	Input
Biodiversity Occurrence Data	External	Input
IUCN data on habitats, threats, protection categories + Red Lists (Spain and Catalonia)	External	Input
Expert knowledge on ecological parameters	External	Input
Camera traps data (apart from GBIF)	AD4GD	Input
Connectivity output: Graphab	AD4GD	Intermediate
Connectivity output: Miramon	AD4GD	Intermediate
Connectivity output: ATOS ML	AD4GD	Intermediate

⁶⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2665963821000130>

⁶⁸ <https://www.creaf.cat/en/research/research-directory/gis-miramon>

Outputs from connectivity as they are presented to end users.	AD4GD	Output
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Table 4 Datasets in use in Pilot 2.

Habitat connectivity data from either approach can then be compared to biodiversity occurrence data sourced from GBIF⁶⁹.

4.3.1 DATASET TRUSTWORTHINESS

LULC Maps. These include an LULC for Catalonia produced by CREAM and the UKCEH (UK level land cover map) produced by Centre for Ecology and Hydrology. Of particular interest is that some LULC maps contain confusion matrices as part of their metadata.

Open Street Map data. Open Street Map data is created by a network of volunteers vectorising satellite observations and incorporating direct observations. As such the spatial inaccuracy in any given feature is very low. However, the more relevant source of uncertainty is misclassification of feature types. Sensitivity to this could be tested by simulated mislabelling though this would require the development of a model of what kinds of mislabelling are most likely. We may need to create an instance of this data on GeoNetwork to provide additional documentation.

World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA). This dataset is to further enrich the initial LULC maps based on the modelling assumption that protected areas will present a lower barrier to species migration. Similarly to the Open Street Map data, this dataset has very little spatial inaccuracy. Instead, the uncertainty lies in deciding upon modelling the effect these areas will have on species connectivity.

Expert knowledge on ecological parameters. This includes modelling assumptions and information from the literature such as maximum dispersal distance for a particular species.

Connectivity estimates. Estimates from the three methods Graphab, Miramon and the ML approach will present a good opportunity to embed the data processing steps as LI_Lineage elements into their metadata records.

GBIF Biodiversity Occurrence Data. Data on GBIF comes from a variety of sources including citizen scientists as well as research institutions. As such the observations can vary a lot in quality. Within pilot 2 we are actively exploring avenues to ameliorate this.

Camera Traps Data. Deployed in the north-east Catalonia, in the Albera Natural Park, these camera traps collect images of animals from which species can be identified.

4.3.2 CALIBRATION AND GROUND TRUTHING

The camera trap data will provide some ability to validate the model output but habitat connectivity measures are generally quite difficult to ground truth.

An approach to uncertainty propagation could involve using the confusion matrices provided with LULC maps. Following this approach we will selectively mislabel regions in the LULC maps according to probabilities provided by their confusion matrices. The UKCEH LULC also provides a per pixel confidence level.

⁶⁹ <https://www.gbif.org/>

4.4 PILOT 3 AIR QUALITY

Figure 46 Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 3.

Pilot 3 focusses on evaluating the potential usefulness of IoT derived air quality data for future forecasting applications. The IoT dataset, the majority of which is derived from the Sensor.Community (formerly Luftdaten) project, is standardised, analysed for outliers and constrained or scaled using the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) air quality forecast analysis data.

For the rescaling, a machine learning model with meteorological variables (e.g. from the ERA5) is trained. The scaled data are then finally compared with in situ reference measurements from official air quality monitoring stations of various European environmental authorities provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA). The focus of this activity is mainly on aerosol air pollutants such as “coarse” particulate matter (PM10) and fine particulate matter (PM2.5).

4.4.1.1 DATASET TRUSTWORTHINESS

Name	Source	Input/Output
Pilot 1	Was this data created within AD4GD?	How does this data fit into the dataflow of the pilot?
CAMS Air Quality Forecast	External	Input

ERA5 Reanalysis Weather Data	External	Input
Sensor.Community Data	External	Input
Upscaled Air Quality nowcast	AD4GD	Output
Sensor.Community Station Trustworthiness measure	AD4GD	Output

Table 5 Datasets in use in Pilot 3

Pilot 3 has two main input datasets and two main outputs. The inputs are IoT data from Sensor.Community and CAMS Air Quality Forecast data. The outputs are an upscaled air quality nowcast and a computed measure of the trustworthiness of the data being produced by each Sensor.Community station. We will look at each dataset through the lens of the data trust worthiness framework.

Sensor.Community is a citizen science project collecting air quality measurements using low cost hardware installed and maintained by volunteers. The project organizers have created tools and materials that allow any individual to build and deploy their own IoT air quality sensors. These individual sensors can be configured to report readings back to Sensor.Community servers and other platforms. Sensor.Community compiles an open-data archive⁷⁰ of all the readings since 2015, in addition serving a real time snapshot that is used to power a web map⁷¹.

Sensor Type	Number	% of Total
SDS011	24029	49%
BME280	10240	21%
DHT22	9352	19%
DNMS (Laerm)	1082	2%
SPS30	771	2%
PMS5003	533	1%
BMP280	509	1%
SHT31	500	1%

Table 6 The selection of Sensor.Community sensor types that reported data within a 5 minute sample interval in January 2024. Sensors that make up less than 1% of the total number of sensors have been omitted for brevity.

Table 6 shows the most common sensor types in use by the Sensor.Community project. The most common configuration (see Figure 1) for a sensor node is an SDS011 particulate matter sensor paired with a BME280 temperature, pressure and humidity sensor. The original recommendation for this later sensor was the DHT22 though this was later updated to the BME280 due to humidity saturation problems with the DHT22.

⁷⁰ <https://archive.sensor.community/>

⁷¹ <https://sensor.community/>

Figure 47 The core hardware for the most common Sensor.Community sensor configuration. Clockwise from left: A 5V power source, a BME280 temperature, pressure and humidity sensor, SDS011 particulate matter and an ESP8266 microcontroller breakout board.

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. shows the readings from active Sensor.Community sensors in Europe. The project has good coverage in Germany and Eastern Europe, with relatively more sparse coverage in France, Spain and Italy.

Figure 48 A screenshot of the Sensor.Community web map showing PM2.5 particulate matter readings. (retrieved 29/10/2024)

Sensor.Community data provides an interesting case study for the data trustworthiness framework. Part of pilot 3 is about performing ground truthing of the Sensor.Community data against the CAMS Air Quality

forecast data. So, on this axis AD4GD is enriching the already existing data with additional trustworthiness information.

Figure 49 Ozone level forecasts from the CAMS Air Quality Forecast showing the 11 different constituent models and the combined results (top left).

CAMS Air Quality Forecast. The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service produces specific daily air quality analyses and forecasts for the European domain at significantly higher spatial resolution (0.1 degrees, approx. 10km) than is available from global analyses and forecasts. The production is based on an ensemble of eleven air quality forecasting systems across Europe. A median ensemble⁷² is calculated from 11 individual outputs of different numerical air quality models. Such ensemble products are advantageous since they yield on average better performance than the individual model products.

For the trustworthiness framework within Pilot 3, we focus on the model analysis data set. The analysis combines model data with observations provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA) into a complete and consistent dataset using various data assimilation techniques depending upon the air-quality forecasting system used. Here, it is important to mention that the assimilated observations from EEA mainly represent so-called background stations. Thus, the model does not include measurements within urban areas. The CAMS forecast comes with extensive quality reports⁷³.

The analysis data is available at hourly time steps and multiple height levels. However, since the IoT/CitizenScience sensors are installed close to the ground, only the lowermost height level is considered in the calculations of the Pilot 3 trustworthiness framework.

ERA5 Reanalysis Weather Data. ERA5 is the fifth generation ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather for the past 8 decades providing data from 1940 onwards. The reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent dataset using the laws of physics. This principle, called data assimilation, is based on the method used by numerical weather

⁷² Note that this is slightly different to some other ensemble weather forecasts which use the same model with different initial conditions.

⁷³<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/CAMS+Regional%3A+European+air+quality+analysis+and+forecast+data+documentation>

prediction centres, where every so many hours a previous forecast is combined with newly available observations in an optimal way to produce a new best estimate of the state of the atmosphere, called analysis, from which an updated, improved forecast is issued. Reanalysis works in the same way, but at reduced resolution to allow for the provision of a dataset spanning back several decades. Reanalysis does not have the constraint of issuing timely forecasts, so there is more time to collect observations, and when going further back in time, to allow for the ingestion of improved versions of the original observations, which all benefit the quality of the reanalysis product.

ERA5 provides hourly estimates for a large number of atmospheric, ocean-wave and land-surface quantities. For Pilot 3, we focus on surface observations, i.e. 2m air and dewpoint temperature, and surface pressure.

4.4.2 CALIBRATION AND GROUND TRUTHING

Unlike Pilots 1 and 2, calibration and ground truthing constitutes the main focus of pilot 3. Hence this section will be significantly more in depth than the previous two projects.

The use of IoT data sets presents several challenges, particularly in the context of low-cost sensors. A key issue is the lack of comprehensive documentation, which can impede the proper understanding and application of the data collected. Additionally, these devices are often not robust, with vulnerabilities in their electronic components, making them prone to failures. Maintenance is another challenge, as these sensors are frequently managed by non-experts, leading to inconsistent upkeep and performance. Moreover, while data correction using reference stations is a common practice, it is often not feasible, further complicating the reliability and accuracy of the collected data.

4.4.2.1 OUTLIER DETECTION

In a first step of Pilot 3's outlier detection scheme, the raw time series of the IoT measurements are standardized in a preliminary preprocessing. This involves resampling uneven temporal data to hourly intervals, taking the median within the respective time interval, and removing invalid measurements as defined by the sensor documentation (≤ 1 or $\geq 999 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

Figure 50 Histogram of $\ln(a)$ for one IoT observation for one time step.

These evenly sampled measurements can now be combined with air quality data from NWP models. Here, we apply a data-driven approach, in which we combine IoT sensor data with the hourly CAMS Europe air quality forecast (0.1°x0.1° grid, Marécal et al., 2015) in order to calculate the ratio

$$\alpha = \frac{X_{IoT}}{X_{CAMS}}$$

for every pollutant (in our case only PM2.5 and PM10). For each time step and IoT observation, $\ln(\alpha)$ is analysed within varying distance radii (50, 25, 10, and 5 km) from the measurement site. Using quartiles and inter-quartile distances, whiskers are calculated to detect and flag outliers. As an example, **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** and **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** demonstrate the outlier filtering for one single observation as well as for a complete time series of one measurement site.

This scheme allows interested users to choose the strictness of their filter criteria dependent on their case study. Moreover, as this scheme is not based on absolute values but solely on the measurement statistics themselves, there is the potential to easily adopt it to other air pollutants such as ozone or nitrogen oxides.

Figure 51 Exemplary time series of filter scheme for one IoT station over several hours.
The red lines indicate the derived thresholds/whiskers for outlier detection.

4.4.2.2 CORRECTION OF IoT MEASUREMENTS

As mentioned above, one would typically use reference stations with a higher confidence level to correct biases of IoT observations. However, air quality usually consist only of a few measurements sites and air pollution exhibits strong spatial gradients (in particular in urban areas). Thus, the correction rather corresponds to an adjustment or rescaling instead of a bias removal.

As a basic condition, we assume that large-scale spatiotemporal averages from CAMS European air quality analyses can be considered to be close to the “truth”. Based on this assumption, we implemented the following correction procedure: First, $\ln(\alpha)$ is binned to the CAMS Europe grid. Then, we select grid cells with sufficient IoT stations and observations and smooth time series, for instance via a 4-week or 2-month running mean.

The measurements principle of the IoT PM sensors is based on the radiative properties of particulate matter (or rather aerosols) in the near infrared spectral range. These properties, more precisely the mass extinction coefficient, highly depends on atmospheric conditions, in particular relative humidity, but to a lesser extent also air temperature. Hence, we train a machine learning model (XGBoost) using meteorological data from ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2023; see Sect. 3.2.3.1) and consider 2m air temperature, 2m relative humidity, and surface pressure, and more as feature input in order to predict $\ln(\alpha)$. Finally, the predicted logarithmic ratio is used to rescale IoT observations.

In the case of PurpleAir devices, a 5-piece equation model from Johnson Barkjohn et al. (2021) is applied specifically for PM_{2.5} correction.

4.4.2.3 PRELIMINARY INTERCOMPARISONS TO REFERENCE STATIONS

First intercomparisons were conducted during winter 2022/23 and summer 2023 in Sofia (Bulgaria) and Brussels (Belgium), using ground-based PM₁₀ measurements from EEA stations as a reference for the uncorrected as well as corrected IoT time series.

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. illustrates the respective area-averaged PM₁₀ concentration for the respective cities. In winter, both the uncorrected and corrected IoT data show very good agreement with high temporal correlation to the reference observations. However, in summer, the (not corrected) IoT data exhibited a systematic low bias, though the short-term variability appears to be in line with the reference data. After applying corrections, the low biases observed in summer are reduced. Although some biases remain, these initial results are promising, yet highlight the need for further fine-tuning.

Figure 52 Time series of area-averaged PM₁₀ concentration in Sofia (top row) and Brussels (bottom row) for winter 2022/23 (left) and summer 2023 (right). The orange line represents average based on EEA stations and shaded and the thick blue lines represent the average based on the raw and corrected IoT measurements, respectively.

4.5 DATA TRUSTWORTHINESS FRAMEWORK CONCLUSIONS

The developing Data Trustworthiness Framework defined in this section provides a systematic approach for assessing and documenting the quality of datasets utilized within the AD4GD project, ensuring that each dataset's reliability is accurately communicated to users. By establishing and applying guidelines that cover both determining and representing data uncertainty in metadata, the framework aims to enable a comprehensive evaluation of data integrity.

Essential methodologies like ground truthing, data lineage tracing, uncertainty quantification, and user feedback incorporation form the core of this framework, allowing datasets from diverse sources, such as satellite observations, Citizen Science, IoT sensors, and administrative records, to be analysed and rated for trustworthiness. The framework emphasizes the need for granular metadata—potentially down to individual observations—and interoperable quality metadata through QualityML. This enables stakeholders to access trustworthy data and make informed, data-driven decisions, reinforcing the overall integrity and transparency of the AD4GD dataspace.

Some key takeaways for the Data Trustworthiness Framework from the datasets used the pilot projects:

Diverse Data Quality Requirements: Each pilot uses different types of datasets (satellite data, Citizen Science, IoT sensors, administrative records), each with unique quality challenges. This highlights that data quality requirements are highly context-dependent and should be tailored to the specific use case within each pilot. For example, spatial resolution is crucial for water and biodiversity monitoring but may be less critical for general air quality assessments.

Importance of Metadata Consistency: The integration of heterogeneous datasets into a coherent framework underscores the need for standardized, high-quality metadata. Consistent metadata, especially following ISO 19115 and QualityML standards, is essential for interoperability across datasets from different domains. This standardization supports transparent documentation of quality metrics and lineage, which is vital for establishing data trustworthiness.

Ground Truthing is a Core Trust-Building Mechanism: Ground truthing plays a central role in validating data sources like IoT sensors and Citizen Science inputs. By comparing these with more trusted datasets, each pilot establishes a baseline for trustworthiness in lower-accuracy, cost-effective data sources, creating a "chain of trust" across sources.

Uncertainty Propagation: In the absence of direct ground truth data, uncertainty quantification and propagation are critical. Pilot 2 shows that models and derived data require careful documentation of propagated uncertainty, especially when combining observational and predictive datasets. This step is essential for transparency and user confidence in data-driven decisions.

Value of User Feedback: All pilots highlight the value of user feedback to improve data quality and usability. Incorporating a structured feedback mechanism, like the Geospatial User Feedback (GUF) model, allows continuous quality monitoring and adjustments based on real-world use cases. This user-centered approach enriches the metadata and aligns data products with user expectations and requirements.

Balancing Completeness with Practicality: Completeness of data quality information is ideal but not always feasible, as seen in Citizen Science and IoT data in Pilots 1 and 3. The framework should allow for a balance, ensuring critical quality metrics are documented without overburdening contributors, particularly in community-driven data collection efforts.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This document has been focused on the following technical components identified and deployed as part of the AD4GD data space: Component 2 – Evaluation of Connector Solutions; Component 9 – Data catalogue and Metadata; and Component 11 – Data Trustworthiness Framework.

Regarding the Evaluation of Connector Solutions, the AD4GD has implemented an IDSA and DSSC aligned data connector integrated with its repository, to facilitate data sharing across different spaces called the Eclipse Data Connector. This connector allows AD4GD to function as a data provider, exposing pilot datasets, and as a data consumer, integrating external data sources. By adopting IDSA standards, AD4GD aligns itself with broader European data initiatives such as Gaia-X and FIWARE, aiming to contribute to a unified data ecosystem. A test scenario involving data exchange between two IDSA-compliant instances was conducted. This test demonstrated the potential for seamless dataset transactions between producer and consumer and sets a foundation for further integration in upcoming project deliverables. The EDC version 0.7 neither allows for path nor query parameters and it is limited to static assets. The support of path and query parameters is critical to allow data exchange via the OGC APIs.

Referring to the Data catalogue and Metadata, the AD4GD has implemented a data and metadata catalogue based on a GeoNetwork instance, focusing on its support for ISO 19115:2003 compliant metadata and integration with other technical components in the dataspace. Despite the availability of the updated versions of the standard, we chose to use ISO 19115:2003, as it remains the most widely adopted version across the geospatial community. GeoNetwork is utilized for organizing geospatial and environmental datasets, providing structured data access through OGC-compliant services like CSW (Catalogue Service for the Web). It has been demonstrated how to link metadata with datasets and how to integrate quality metrics using QualityML and semantics links all around the data using an ISO 19139 mechanism for anchors. GeoNetwork also supports the DCAT metadata standard recommended by the DSSC, making it feasible to adapt the proposed AD4GD implementation with the DSSC specifications. At this moment, it is unclear if the data connector integrated catalogue will replace the GeoNetwork in the long run.

The deliverable also analyzes the Data Trustworthiness Framework and looks at how these tools can be used to implement a framework for tracking data quality and trustworthiness as data flow through each pilot pipeline. This includes the form and prevalence of uncertainty information attached to external datasets used in the project, methods for estimating uncertainty information when it is missing, uncertainty propagation, groundtruthing and standardised representations for this information.